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Harmful Algal Bloom Initiation and Prediction in Large European Marine Ecosystems

HABILE

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HABILE - Final Scientific Report

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SECTION 5: EXECUTIVE PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY (FINAL REPORT)

Contract n°	EVK3-2001-00063	Project duration:	01/01/02 – 31/12/04
Title	HABILE – Harmful Algae bloom Initiation and Prediction in Large European Marine Ecosystems.		
<p>Objectives:</p> <p>The overall objectives of the HABILE project is to better understand the processes that lead to Harmful Algae Bloom (HAB) events in European coastal waters by;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • characterisation of the most frequent and harmful algae bloom events and related region-specific species and assemblage during the last decade for three major European Large marine ecosystem's – the Baltic Sea, North Sea and adjacent Scandinavian waters and the Northern Iberian coast i.e. the Galician Rias; • analysis and re-evaluation of combined medium to long-term data sets (<i>in situ</i> and satellite observations from the three study regions) and • model simulations of the environmental conditions and factors for the initiation growth and decay (life cycle) of at least three identified HAB species related to the three study regions of the project. <p>Scientific achievements:</p> <p>In the HABILE project environmental and biological data (in situ and satellite EO, both historical and newly acquired data) for three regional European marine ecosystems, all hampered by HAB events – i.e. the Baltic Sea, North Sea/Skagerrak and Galician Rias - have been analysed in order to identify the specific biological, chemical and/or physical HAB triggering factors.</p> <p>Assessment and comparisons of data products from three different satellite Earth observation (EO) ocean colour sensors - SeaWiFS, MODIS and MERIS – have been under taken. EO studies have been undertaken in order to study the inherent optical properties for development of new statistical methods for better discrimination HAB events in contrast to other algal blooms.</p> <p>In order to investigate the optimal data assimilation parameterisation for HAB simulations, twin experiments with a generic Ensemble Kalman Filter have been undertaken. These conclude that nutrients assimilation performs well during well-mixed stratified conditions (winter), however phytoplankton biomass assimilation outperformed nutrients assimilation during the algae growth season.</p> <p>Specie specific information for the pre-dominant regional HAB species have been selected in order to parameterize and identify the key processes for the regional HAB triggering factors. These HAB parameterizations have been used to improve existing marine ecosystem models including algae modules. Scenario simulation studies have been performed for respectively the three geographical regions in order to reproduce the bloom initiation, development and decay. Model conceptions have been developed respectively for cyanobacteria blooms (both the toxin producing <i>Nodularia spumigena</i> and <i>Aphanizomenon</i>) in the Baltic Sea, for the flagellate <i>Chattonella</i> spp. in the North Sea/Skagerrak region, as well as <i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i> for the Galician Rias.</p> <p>Regional model simulations performed during early spring 2004 for the Baltic Sea includes two prediction scenarios for the development of cyanobacteria during the following summer. The early monitoring results were used to derive the indicators as initial conditions for the ecosystem model. The scenarios were based on the initial condition in early February 2004 and the atmospheric forcing development of the years 2000 (a cold summer) and 2002 (a warm summer). Both scenarios gave a high biomass for cyanobacteria in the Gulf of Finland area, with small variations in the north-south abundance distribution within the Gulf. The high level of the biomass is rooted in the high levels of phosphate, whereas the variations in the spatial cyanobacterial distribution between the scenarios are effected by variations the mean circulation regime.</p>			

For the Galician Rias Baixas the triggering factors of harmful dinoflagellate initiation is hypothesized to coincide with downwelling and low runoff (coastal downwelling: runoff ratio ≥ 7) during the autumn season, when dinoflagellates are present in the microplankton community. Downwelling excludes diatoms from the competition for nutrients. Bloom development needs the return to weak upwelling conditions, which then supply nutrients for dinoflagellate growth. The model simulations indicate that the upwelling mediation of the nutrient fertilization of the Ria is very important, in particular during the spring and summer. However, the effect of river nutrients also produces important changes to the pelagic ecosystem. It is the coupling of the two fertilization paths, which generated the highest integrated production. Only short-lived strong downwelling winds caused biomass from the shelf to accumulate inside the Ria, thus supporting our initial hypothesis. Additionally the simulations indicate that while there were changes to summer integrated N to P ratios in the different scenarios, they were small and unlikely to produce large shifts in phytoplankton community composition.

Model scenario simulations for the North Sea/Skagerrak region support the need for proper model resolving of the meso-scale physical oceanographic processes (5-10 kilometre) in order to be able to simulate the variability in the ecosystem and HAB components of a coupled marine ecosystem model. HAB occurrences have a strong sensitivity to the physical mixed layer dynamics (wind conditions) and the duration of calm periods are essential for bloom initiation and lifetime.

Main deliverables:

Twelve major project reports are delivered covering the major work packages of the project; WP1. Regional Studies of HAB Events, WP2. HAB Dynamics and Life Cycles, WP3. 1-D Algal Cycle Modelling, WP4. 3-D Coupled Ecosystem Modelling, WP5. Assessment of trend and future possibility of EO data for HAB monitoring, WP6. Data assimilation experiments for Ecosystem Models, WP7. Scenario definitions, WP8. Assemble Model Simulations and Prediction, WP9. Environmental Impact Assessment and Scenario Evaluation, WP10. Socio-Economic Impact Assessment, WP11. HABILE Final Data Set and WP9 HABILE Final Assessment Synthesis. A summary of the publications is given below.

Socio-economic relevance and policy implications:

Addressing the socio-economic impact of HAB events, a general methodology has been developed for *ex post* assessment studies taking into account the impact HAB events have in the various countries surrounding the European waters studied.

Several of the HABILE developed HAB monitoring and modelling tools will be further used in the on-going and future marine monitoring and modelling activities related to GMES, such as in the ESA GSE marine services, in the EC FP6 IP MERSEA and other national and international initiatives related to monitoring of HAB's in European waters.

Conclusions:

HABILE has significantly improved the scientific foundation for the monitoring and prediction of HAB's hampering human activities in three major European coastal/marine ecosystems. During the project the four regional ecosystem models are in operation for respectively the North Sea/Skagerrak, The Baltic Sea and Galician Rias has been implemented, expanded and assessed with dedicated HAB modules at gender specific level. Monitoring and early warning methodologies for identification of possible HAB events have been developed and evaluated. Scenario ecosystem simulations had been done and impact assessments performed. The link to nutrient loads and balances for the HAB occurrences are drawn however the triggering factors also include the biological and physical initial and development conditions. The approach of an integrated monitoring, including *in situ* and satellite EO data sources, data assimilation tools and numerical model predictions are a requisite for efficient monitoring and forecasting of HAB events. The socio-economic impact of HAB has been studied and a methodology for its impact assessment suggested.

Dissemination of results:

Under HABILE four peer-review articles have been published during the course of the project. Furthermore two papers have been accepted for publication and four are under review by the end of the project. One chapter contribution to a book has been accepted for publication in 2005. Additionally 10 peer-review papers are under preparation for submission and eventual publication during 2005. One book "Monitoring of Harmful Algae Blooms - The contribution by remote

sensing” is under preparation to be published by Springer-Praxis. HABILE project results have been presented orally or as poster at about 30 relevant scientific and managerial conferences, most with proceedings of papers or extended abstracts. A project web-site has been established and maintained under the project - <http://www.nersc.no/HABILE/>.

Keywords: Harmful algae blooms, ecosystem dynamics, modelling, scenario simulations and socio-economic impact.

1 BACKGROUND

In the last two decades a noticeable increase in the occurrence of the marine and coastal “Harmful Algal Blooms”, so called HAB’s, has been recorded. HAB may develop rapidly with a significant increase in the local population of microscopic and macroscopic algae that can cause harm to the environment and human activities in a multitude of ways. Some toxic phytoplankton species are consumed by filter-feeding organisms, leading to different types of illness in human consumers eating the e.g. shellfish. During the last fifteen years, economic losses to fisheries and aquaculture industry have been reported in various European marine waters. The most noxious effects have been reported in European large marine ecosystems (LME), i.e. the North Sea and Skagerrak regions (e.g. *Chrysochromulina polylepis* in 1988 and *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* in 1998 and 2000), the Northern Iberian coast - Galician Rías (*Gymnodinium catenatum*), and in the Baltic Sea, where toxic blooms of blue-green algae (cyanobacteria *Nodularia spumigena*) are annual HAB phenomena. In addition to toxicity, phytoplankton blooms are often harmful by fouling fishing gears, and smearing beaches causing economic losses, by lowering the recreational value of the recreational coastal area.

Although a great deal is known about the ecology and physiology of harmful algae, major gaps still exist in our understanding of the factors controlling the population dynamics, including initiation, of HAB. For these reasons it is of fundamental importance a) to reach a better understanding on the environmental conditions and assemblage properties of the main HAB events occurring in European coastal waters, b) to improve our capability to simulate HAB events, and c) to assess how the apparent increase in frequency of HAB is related to an increased anthropogenic forcing on the marine environment.

HAB can occur in a matter of days, and can disappear just as rapidly, and may be geographically limited or extend over huge areas. Blooms generally mark a convergence of factors that encourage phytoplankton growth. The factors that cause algal blooms to occur can be anthropogenic or natural, including: introduction through deballasting of large boats or transportation of living shellfish; or an algae specie present in a “favourable” environment defined by available sunlight, amount and composition of the nutrients, water temperature and hydrodynamics. Various species have different optimal growth conditions, e.g., related to nutrients, which may set an “hierarchical organisation” or succession of blooms during the growth seasons. In addition, the biological cycle of the individual algal species, and the prey/predator conditions, influence the bloom development and decay conditions. All factors that determine the intensity and biological cycle of a bloom are complex and still not fully understood. Mechanisms that contribute to the termination of a bloom include hydrodynamical and wind-driven transport, as well as the bloom triggering factors mentioned above - lack of nutrients, reduction in solar radiation and water temperature to a certain extent.

It is “suggested strongly” that anthropogenic activities might be responsible for the observed increase of reported HAB events in the last decades. The main human induced impact is the fertilisation of the marine environment through changes in the amount and composition of the nutrient reservoir made available to primary producers (e.g. through transfer of air pollution, agricultural discharge). Therefore it is important to assess and quantify the impact of changes in the amount of nutrient if recommendations are to be provided to decision- and policy-makers towards the advancement of conventions for the reduction of nutrient loads of the sea. It has been suggested that HAB events might be reduced, by controlling the nutrient availability and composition. It has also been reported that over-fishing of selective species might unbalance the ecosystem through a decrease of grazing upon herbivores, which might result in an increase of algal blooms including HAB.

2 OBJECTIVES

The overall objectives of the HABILE - Harmful Algae Bloom Initiation and Prediction in Large European Marine Ecosystems project are as follows:

- To better understand the processes that lead to HAB events by a) the characterisation of the most frequent and harmful algae bloom events and related region-specific species and assemblage (e.g. cyanobacteria *Nodularia spumigena*, flagellates *Chattonella sp.*, *Gymnodinium catenatum*) during the last decade for three major European LME – the Baltic Sea, North Sea and adjacent Scandinavian waters, and the Northern Iberian coast. b) the analysis and re-evaluation of combined medium to long-term data sets (*in situ* and satellite observations from the three study regions), and c) the characterisation of the environmental conditions and factors for the initiation, growth and decay (life cycle) of at least three identified HAB species related to the three study regions of this project.
- To model the response of the identified species to variable environmental conditions with focus on anthropogenic impacts through nutrient enrichment and change in nutrient ratios.
- To improve existing HAB-related numerical ecosystem models, and in turn the capability to simulate the occurrence and extent of future HAB events under various environmental and anthropogenic development scenarios.
- To assess through use of model simulation scenarios, the impact that changes in nutrient compound may have on a) initiation of a monospecific bloom, b) the competition between algal species and the succession of monospecific or diverse blooms during the growth season.
- To assess the economic impact a reduction of HAB will have on fisheries, food, and tourism industries by establishing a project users and reference group in order to disseminate and communicate the project results on HAB events to authorities, regional marine Commissions (HELCOM, OSPAR) EC and agencies responsible for the formulation of relevant policies.

3 APPLIED METHODOLOGY, SCIENTIFIC ACHIVEMENTS AND MAIN DELIVERABLES

In HABILE long-term data sets of *in situ* and satellite Earth observation measurements related to Harmfull Algae Bloom (HAB) events, are combined and analysed in order to characterise and model the bio-geochemical and physical conditions and processes leading to the bloom formation, development and decay. Comparison of three geographical regions in European waters has been performed – i.e. the Baltic Sea, North Sea/Skagerrak and Galician Rias. All these regions are regularly hampered by HAB events respectively the cyanobacteria blooms (both the toxin producing *Nodularia spumigena* and *Aphanizomenon*) in the Baltic Sea, the flagellate *Chattonella* spp. in the North Sea/Skagerrak region, as well as *Gymnodinium catenatum* for the Galician Rias. A similar methodological approach has been applied in order to identify and parameterize the HAB triggering, development and decay factors (including biological, chemical and physical conditions) in all three regions. The different regional results and conclusions will be subsequently presented in this section.

3.1 *Chattonella* spp. in the North Sea/Skagerrak region

During the year 1997 to 2002, the flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* has formed three larger blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat region, in the years 1998, 2000, and 2001 respectively. During the first and the last blooms fish mortality was registered in fish farms along the southern coast of Norway. It is likely that the species initially, in 1998, was introduced to the area and that it during the following years has been further spread within the area and now is well established in the region.

A short summary of the previous *Chattonella* bloom scenarios are given in, Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of *Chattonella* blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak and Kattegat – 1997-2002.

Summary of the inter annual bloom variability of *Chattonella* spp. in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area 1997-2002

1997: No large scale *Chattonella* bloom but a local bloom was observed in the Århus Bugt, Denmark.

1998: First *Chattonella* bloom year. The bloom originated at the west coast of Jutland and it was transported northward along the west coast by the Jutland current. The major part of the bloom patch is supposed to be advected over from Denmark to the southern part of Norway as a result of blockage in the eastward direction due to the Baltic out flow in the Kattegat. Part of the bloom might have spread to the Swedish west coast, crossing under the Baltic out-flow current. Following the transport to the southern part of Norway the bloom spread to the Swedish coast due to east/south eastern currents compensating the Baltic outflow in the surface.

1999: No *Chattonella* bloom.

2000: Second *Chattonella* bloom year – only in the North Sea. No passage northward to the Swedish west coast and the southern part of Norway – presumably due to blockage of the Jutland current south of Skagen.

2001: Third *Chattonella* bloom year – mainly in the Kattegat/Skagerrak area. Low concentrations in the part of the North Sea – it is assumed that the bloom originated and developed in Kattegat and successively in the Baltic out-flow current which transported the bloom to the Norwegian coast.

2002: No *Chattonella* bloom

It is generally assumed that one of the major factors responsible for the occurrence of high biomass HAB's in the North Sea area is eutrophication, which is caused by excess load of the nutrients nitrogen and phosphorous to the coastal waters. Eutrophication is mainly a result of anthropogenic activities such as agriculture and production of industrial and municipal waste water. Evidence of eutrophication, such as algal blooms, oxygen deficiency and fish and invertebrate kills in the coastal waters of the North Sea, started to accumulate in the beginning of the 1980's. In e.g. Denmark this led to the implementation of an action plan called the "aquatic environmental plan" in 1986. The major goals of the plan were to reduce the load of phosphorous and nitrogen to the aquatic environment with 80 and 50% respectively. The goal for reduction of the phosphorous load was reached in 1995/96 where as the goal for reduction of the nitrogen load has only partly been met. In 1998 it was concluded that the nitrogen load was reduced with approx. 63% of the goal, leaving 37% of the excess load still to be handled.

The *Chattonella* blooms were all observed in the coastal water masses, which are characterised by shallow water, or a shallow pycnocline, relatively low salinity and relatively high availability of nutrients due to run-off from land and regeneration of nutrient from the sediment. Distinct coastal water masses, e.g. revealed by a distinct temperature signal, are characteristic for *Chattonella* bloom areas at the West Coast of Denmark as well as along the West Coast of Sweden and along the South Norwegian coast, Figure 1.

Figure 1: Weekly averages of sea surface temperature (°C) for the period January-May 1998 derived from the NOAA AVHRR sensor.

The first bloom of *Chattonella* in North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area was observed in 1998. The species was identified as *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*. The bloom was observed at the west coast of Denmark in the beginning of April, and spread out to cover the area from the German bight, along the west coast of Denmark, Sweden, and the southern coast of Norway up to Bokn fjord during April and May. The highest concentrations were recorded at the west coast of Denmark. At the time, this was the first observation of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak but re-analysis of material from the Swedish west coast showed that *Chattonella* has been present in rather low concentrations since 1990, most likely overlooked in routine investigations (L. Edler, pers. com.). In late April 2000 a new bloom of *Chattonella* sp. was observed in the southern part of the west coast of Denmark. This time the bloom occurred from the German Bight to Skagen (northern part of Jylland, Denmark) during late April to mid May (Lu & Göbel, 2000). The latest bloom in the Skagerrak area occurred in March-April 2001. The bloom was first observed at the Swedish west coast in the beginning of March, spreading to the southern coast of Norway during the second half of March. In the beginning of April the bloom covered the Swedish west coast and the southern coast of Norway to Mandal. The bloom disappeared from the area approximately 20 April.

For *Chattonella* blooms to form based upon in-situ growth it can be calculated that a pre-bloom period of 2-3 weeks is required for the bloom to develop. During the pre-bloom/initiation period wind must be weak to minimise dispersion of *Chattonella* cells and inorganic nutrients in the coastal waters into the North Sea. Furthermore, light and nutrient must be available to promote growth. Both these conditions are – in some years – met during April/May – high-pressure periods in the North Sea area.

Since the bloom in 1998, researchers have been aware of the presence of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak area and the species has been included in the routine monitoring of harmful algae in the countries surrounding the area. Monitoring data shows that *Chattonella* is present in the area during spring every year and has in a way become a natural part of the late spring phytoplankton.

A conceptual model for an algae bloom scenario consist of a succession of several phases:

Phase 1. Pre-bloom phase – the species is only present in very low concentrations in the pelagic or alternatively is present in the sediment in encysted form. To proceed to the next phase of the bloom development, the cysts must germinate and the encysted specimens enters the pelagic environment.

Phase 2. Growth phase - The species present in the pelagic now enters the growth phase. The major parameters determining the growth rate at the cell level are the availability of light and inorganic nutrients, temperature, salinity and in some cases turbulence. On the population level the population growth rate is a combination of the physiological growth process in combination with loss processes such as grazing, sedimentation e.g. during encystment (vertical) and dispersion/advection (horizontal and vertical).

Phase 3. “Bloom” phase - The species enters the bloom phase when it reaches a maximum concentration in time. This concentration or concentration level can be maintained for some time reaching from hours to months depending upon the bloom species. The maximum concentration can be regarded as a measure of the carrying capacity for the species in the specific system where the bloom occurs. Most often the bloom concentrations is controlled by a combination of light availability and nutrient availability.

Phase 4. “Crash” phase - The bloom is terminated during the bloom decline phase/crash phase. Decline of a bloom can be the result of increased grazing pressure, cease of growth due to lack of inorganic nutrients, encystment, interactions with bacteria and/or virus, and dispersion e.g. due to a storm event. One of the above mention factors can work or a combination of several.

3.1.1 Seasonal and inter-annual bloom variability

The three *Chattonella* blooms observed in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat have occurred during the period from March to the middle of May, Figure 2. Each bloom lasted for approximately 1 month. Even though the blooms have occurred within a narrow time window, there is a tendency for the blooms to occur earlier and earlier for each bloom observed. The 1998 and 2000 blooms were both initiated on the west coast of Denmark

and/or in the German bight in April, spreading northward with the Jutland coastal current along the Danish west coast into the Skagerrak (Figure 3 to Figure 6). After reaching the northern point of Denmark (Skagen) the further spreading is different in the two blooms. The 1998 bloom most likely spread north-west reaching the Norwegian coast, due to the wind condition in that period. The bloom also propagated north-east wards along the Swedish Skagerrak coast, mainly as a sub-surface bloom (based on chlorophyll profiles).

During the 2000 bloom there were not observed any further spreading of the bloom after reaching Skagen. However satellite information indicates that part of the bloom was moved offshore the Danish coast into the open Skagerrak but did not reach the Norwegian coast. During both blooms, 1998 and 2000, the highest concentrations of *Chattonella* were observed west and south of Hanstholm at the Danish North Sea coast, in both years the bloom occurred in April-March.

The 2001 bloom was different from the other blooms in several aspects. The 2001 bloom began 1 month earlier than the other two blooms. The bloom in 2001 occurred just after the spring diatom bloom, or was partly overlapping with the spring bloom, where as the previously blooms occurred well after the spring bloom had collapsed. The bloom most likely started at the southern coast of the Swedish Kattegat coast. The bloom were advected northward with the Baltic out-flow current along the west coast of Sweden. Models of the water circulation in the area, indicates that there was a pronounced outflow from Kattegat to Skagerrak in the beginning of March. At the time of largest coverage of the bloom it covers the whole Swedish west coast and the Norwegian Skagerrak coast down to Mandal. There were no observations of *Chattonella* along the Danish west coast in March 2001, but it was observed in mid April. The bloom was only observed up to the east of Lindesnes. Circulation models for this area indicate that the bloom stopped due to the presence of north-easterly winds and eddies formed in the Lindesnes area, which restricted further advection of the bloom up along the Norwegian coast.

Figure 2: *Chattonella* spp abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003.

Figure 3: Observed abundance cells/l (max. concentration registered in each month) of *Chattonella* spp. at Danish, Swedish and Norwegian monitoring stations during the period January-June 1998.

Figure 4: Observed abundance cells/l (max. concentration registered in each month) of *Chattonella* spp. at Danish, Swedish and Norwegian monitoring stations during the period January-June 2000.

Figure 5: Observed abundance cells/l (max. concentration registered in each month) of *Chattonella* spp. at Danish, Swedish and Norwegian monitoring stations during the period January-June 2001.

Figure 6: Observed abundance cells/l (max. concentration registered in each month) of *Chattonella* spp. at Danish, Swedish and Norwegian monitoring stations during the period January-June 2002.

3.1.2 Vertical distribution of *Chattonella* during the blooms

Vertical profiles of *Chattonella* during the various blooms show that the species is mainly located in the upper meters of the water column. During the bloom in 1998 *Chattonella* was observed down to 30 meters at the Danish Skagerrak coast. The highest abundance was observed in the upper 10 meters. More or less the same pattern was observed in the 2001. High abundance of *Chattonella* was observed above the halocline at most stations. The highest concentrations were measured in the upper 5 meters (Figure 7). However, *Chattonella* may also be present as a sub-surface maximum.

Figure 7: Vertical profile of the distribution of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* at Lyngør during the 2001 bloom. The profile from this station was representative for a larger area along the southern coast of Norway, except for stations influenced by freshwater runoff.

3.1.3 Satellite data information

The methodological result of the HABILE research in this respect is fully outlined in deliverable D.5 **Assessment of trend and future possibility of EO data for HAB monitoring** and the related publications. In this report their applications are only included. Satellite information on chlorophyll and sea surface temperature are available for the whole HABILE investigations area as daily presentations as well as presentations of weekly averages, see e.g. <http://HAB.nersc.no>.

1998: The images displayed in Figure 8, are SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll concentration ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), and show an area of high pigment concentration to the western coast of Denmark (white patterns), which were reported to be dominated by *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*. Land and clouds over the sea are masked in black. The time series shows the development and decay of the bloom between May 15 and May 29. The concentration values range from 40 - 64 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (May 15) to 6-10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (May 29).

1999: No *Chattonella* blooms observed, however increased pigment concentrations during various periods of the bloom season were reported based on the satellite EO data.

2000: On April 18, 2000 a significantly increase in the level of chlorophyll pigment concentration in the SeaWiFS data was observed to occur along the south west coast of Jutland. The phytoplankton biomass was dominated by species from the class Raphidophyceae, most likely the species *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* which was later reported in the waters west off Esbjerg (Figure 9). The development and decay of the bloom was observed in a combination EO and *in situ* data.

2001: A *Chattonella* bloom was observed in March. Since the bloom occurred earlier in the spring season, the cloud cover situation was generally worse than in previous years. This limited the benefits of using optical and infrared satellite Earth observation (EO) data. Figure

10 shows the main decay and progression of the blooms along the south coast of Norway between March 20th and March 25th.

2002: No bloom of *Chattonella*. Rather low concentrations were observed during the spring and summer periods in the Kattegat/Skagerrak area, however other flagellates bloomed (Figure 11).

Figure 8: Pigment concentration distribution in the North Sea and Skagerrak as derived from SeaWiFS data. (a) May 15 1998; (b) May 17 1998; (c) May 29 1998. Copyright NASA SeaWiFS project/Orbital Image Corp. (<http://HAB.nersc.no>).

Figure 9: Time series of SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll-a concentration for May 2000 showing the initiation, development and decay of the *Chattonella* bloom between May 12th and May 24th. (<http://HAB.nersc.no>).

Figure 10: The development of the *Chattonella* bloom in March, 2001 as observed in the pigment concentrations derived from the SeaWiFS data from respectively 20th, 21st, 23rd. and 25th March. Land and clouds are indicated in black, high pigment concentrations in red and orange. (<http://HAB.nersc.no>).

Figure 11: Time series of the SeaWiFS chlorophyll pigment concentrations for the North Sea during the *Chattonella* bloom in March 2001 (<http://HAB.nersc.no>).

3.1.4 Chemical and physical oceanographic conditions

a) Salinity and temperature

Since the different blooms occurred in different areas, there will be rather wide spectra of salinities where *Chattonella* spp. are observed in high abundance. This is due to the mixing of several distinct water masses with marked differences in e.g. salinity.

Chattonella spp. was observed in water masses with salinity from ~12 up to 35 psu (see Figure 12). The highest abundance was observed at salinities between 20 and 34 psu. These observations are backed up by experiments with the Norwegian strain of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* which showed positive growth within the salinity range 15 to 35 psu, whereas the species fail to grow at salinity of less than 10 psu. (Naustvoll, unpubl. data). From the present information it is not expected that *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* can produce harmful blooms in areas with salinities below 12 psu. This dependence of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* on relative high salinities, **excludes it from blooming in the low saline Baltic Proper.**

The broad temperature tolerance of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* (0°C to ~21°C) allows for it to bloom during most of the late winter to spring-early summer in Scandinavian waters. Laboratory experiments shows that the species tolerates temperatures between 0°C and 15°C, with the highest growth rate below 10°C (Naustvoll, unpubl. data). The three distinct tops observed in Figure 13, reflects the timing of the *Chattonella* blooms in the three different blooming years. During the 1998 bloom the water temperature was between 8°C and 12°C; in 2000 approximately 8°C and the 2001 bloom occurred at temperatures between 1°C and 5°C.

Figure 12: *Chattonella* spp. abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the salinity.

Figure 13: *Chattonella* spp. abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the surface seawater temperature.

b) Pre-spring bloom conditions

In 2002 and especially in 1998 exceptionally high concentrations of inorganic-N were observed at stations nearest to the coast, indicating the existence of a distinct coastal water mass in combination with run-off from land. The rest of the years the concentrations were at a rather uniform level. The observed concentrations of inorganic-P were less variable between the years than the inorganic-N concentrations. The concentrations of dissolved silicate were rather high in the years 1998, 2000 and 2002.

c) Run-off and nutrient load

The run-off to the *Chattonella* bloom area varies much throughout the season as well as between the different years.

The winter and spring run-off from the Rhein, which is supposed to be the major source of nutrients to the Jutland water mass, reaches a maximum value during March/April. The highest run-off values are registered in 1999 and 2000, where as the values in March was very low in 1998. Thus blooms of *Chattonella* can occur both in a year with a remarkable low run-off from the river Elbe (1998) and in a year with record high run-off from the river (2000). The load of N and P from the river Elbe does not show much variability between the years. The load of inorganic-N, however, is rather low in the spring of 1998 and 2000 compared to the rest of the years. The load of inorganic-P during April-May 1998 and 2000 are higher than observed in any of the other years.

For phosphate (PO_4), most of the high concentrations of *Chattonella* spp. were observed in water masses with concentrations less than $0,25 \mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$, Figure 14. The 1998 and 2001 blooms occurred in water masses with a rather wide range in the phosphate concentrations. The 2000 bloom data are mostly from the Danish west coast with water masses characterized by low phosphate levels ($\sim 0,05 \mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$).

Figure 14: *Chattonella* spp. abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the PO_4 concentration ($\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$).

Figure 15: *Chattonella* spp. abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the $\text{NO}_2 + \text{NO}_3$ concentration ($\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$).

The 2000 bloom data were collected in the water masses at the southern part of the Danish west coast. These water masses are affected by transport of water from the German Bight, which is rich in N due to high impact of runoff from major European rivers. Most data points from this bloom show high N levels. The 2001 bloom in Kattegat/Skagerrak was located in water masses with lower levels of inorganic nitrogen. The 1998 *Chattonella* bloom was observed in a large area with heterogeneous water masses, which results in a large variation in the levels of inorganic nitrogen observed. Even though the highest biomasses of *Chattonella* was registered in water masses with rather high N concentrations, there is no clear relationship between increasing abundance of *Chattonella* and increased levels of inorganic nitrogen (Figure 15).

Data for the N/P ratio of dissolved nutrients are shown in Figure 16. Observations of high concentrations of *Chattonella* at high N/P ratio are due to the high abundance of *Chattonella* during the 2000 bloom at the west coast of Denmark. These water masses was rich in N but had relatively low P levels. As for N and P there is no obvious relationship between abundance and increasing N/P ratio.

Chattonella is not depending on silicate (SiO_4) for its growth. The data points in shown in Figure 17, are influenced by the timing of the diatom spring bloom and the influence of freshwater runoff into the sampling areas.

Figure 16: *Chattonella* spp abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the N/P ratio.

Figure 17: *Chattonella* spp abundance in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area, during the period 1998 to 2003, plotted against the SiO_4 ($\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$).

d) Meteorology and irradiance

It is assumed that the weather conditions have a direct and indirect influence on bloom formation and transport in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat area. The indirect influence is mainly on the current system that changes due to wind and air pressure. More direct influence is exerted through wind-induced turbulence. Flagellates and the smaller phytoplankton are believed to be well adapted to low turbulence conditions, while diatoms and the larger phytoplankton are believed to have a competitive advantage at moderate turbulence. Low winds usually co-occur with high air pressure and high light conditions.

The wind energy during April/May varies between the years. In 1998, 2000 and 2001 the wind energy were low from mid April to mid May where as, during the same period in 1999 and 2002, the wind energy was higher.

The global irradiance during the spring periods from 1997 to 2002 varies between years. In 1998 and 2000 there was a stable increase in irradiance from mid April to mid May. In 1999 the irradiance breaks down rather early in May and is poorly developed during late April/beginning of May 2002.

e) Effects of temperature and salinity

Based on field data during the blooms in the Skagerrak region and the seasonality of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* this species must be regarded as a “coldwater species”, with bloom formation in water masses of 2°C to 12°C. Laboratory experiments with the Norwegian strain of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*, confirms that the species is a coldwater species, with optimal growth between 5°C and 10°C (Naustvoll, unpubl. data).

Chattonella species are rather euryhaline and grow within a broad range of salinities (e.g. Imai et al 1998, Marshall & Hallegraeff 1999, Naustvoll unpubl. data). However, based on the available information it seems that *Chattonella* species can survive only at salinities above 10-15 (e.g. Imai et al 1998, Marshall & Hallegraeff 1999, Naustvoll unpubl. data).

f) Effect of light

Increasing light intensity result in an increase in the specific growth rate of *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa*, until it become saturated at $\sim 100 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. At the highest light intensity tested ($400 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) the growth rate was reduced, but not significantly different from the growth rate at the saturation intensity. At the lowest light intensity tested ($5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) a growth rate of approx. 0 d^{-1} was observed (Naustvoll, unpubl. data).

g) Loss processes

Grazing: There is not much available data on grazing for *Chattonella* aff. *verruculosa* in the North Sea/Skagerrak/Kattegat region. During the blooms, sampling and quantitative analysis of microzooplankton (ciliates and heterotrophic dinoflagellates) and mesozooplankton (copepods) was not included in the routine monitoring. However, results from the specific *Chattonella* monitoring along the southern coast of Norway in 2001, shows that there was an increase in the concentrations of heterotrophic dinoflagellates during the second half of the bloom. Unfortunately, the counting methods used do not give statistically good result for this group of organisms. Especially two species, *Torodinium robustum* and a small-identified heterotrophic *Gymnodinium* species showed a tendency to increase in the concentrations during this later period of the bloom. Ciliates were seldom observed. The heterotrophic dinoflagellates were observed with food vacuoles, but it was neither possible to identify the contents nor was the ingestion process observed (Naustvoll unpubl. data). The interactions between *Chattonella* and these dinoflagellates as well as other microzooplankton species, should be properly investigated. During the *Chattonella* bloom in 2001, simple incubation experiments with *Calanus* sp. in natural water with high concentration of *Chattonella* were performed. The result from these experiments showed that *Calanus* sp. did not feed on *Chattonella*, nor did *Chattonella* had any negative effect on the survival of the *Calanus* species during the one week incubation (Naustvoll unpubl. data). These findings should be further examined and verified by controlled laboratory experiments.

3.1.5 Modelling of *Chattonella* spp.

In the HABILE project we have concluded to use the NORWegian ECOlogical Model system (NORWECOM) (Aksnes et al, 1995, Skogen et al, 1995, Skogen & Søliland, 1998) together with satellite remote sensing and in situ observations for monitoring and forecasting of HAB events, and *Chattonella* spp. blooms in particular, in the North Sea and Skagerrak waters of Norwegian interest. The modelling system was developed in Bergen, Norway during the 1990's at the Institute of Marine Research (IMR) in cooperation with the University of Bergen (Institute of Fisheries and Marine Biology, Institute of Mathematics) and later with the Norwegian Meteorological institute (Met.no). It has been applied for primary production studies of the North Sea (Skogen & Moll, 2000) and extensively validated in Svendsen et al, (1996, 1996), Berntsen et al, (1996), Skogen et al. (1997), Søliland & Skogen (2000) and Søliland et al, (2003). The remote sensing data is mainly provided by the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), in cooperation with the Plymouth Marine Laboratory (see HABILE deliverable D.5).

NORWECOM is a coupled three-dimensional physical-chemical-biological ocean model system applied to study primary production, dispersion of particles (fish larvae, pollution) and eutrophication (Skogen and Søliland, 1998). For most purposes, NORWECOM has been used in an area covering an extended North Sea with a horizontal resolution of 20 x 20 km (Figure 18, left). This resolution is too coarse to properly model processes within the Skagerrak, and for that purpose a nested version of the model is used. In the nested model, boundary values from the coarse North Sea model are used as input to a fine grid (4 x 4 km) model for the eastern North Sea, Skagerrak and Kattegat (Figure 18, right).

Figure 18: Bottom topography for the nested domains of NORWECOM with coarse (20km, left) and fine (4km, right) grid resolution.

The biological-chemical module of NORWECOM is coupled to the physical model through the subsurface light, the hydrography and the horizontal and the vertical flow and mixing of the water masses. This module is based on Aksnes et al. (1995) who used it in a land-locked fjord in western Norway. After this, the model has been further developed and implemented on a model area covering an extended North Sea. NORWECOM discriminate between two groups of phytoplankton, diatoms (DIA) and flagellates (FLA), and their growth is affected by the nutrient concentrations, light intensity and temperature. The nutrients are represented by inorganic nitrogen (NIT) such as nitrate and ammonia, inorganic phosphorus (PHO) (phosphate) and inorganic silicon (SIL) (silicate). The main difference between diatoms and flagellates is that silicate is not limiting for the production of flagellates. Nutrients are added to the system through river runoff and from the atmosphere. Further nitrogen and phosphorus are regenerated from the dead algae (DET), and silicate from biogenic silica (SIS) at a constant rate. Oxygen (OXY) is released during primary production and it is consumed in respiration and when detrital matter is regenerated. Oxygen is assumed to be saturated at the surface. For both the dead and living algae, a sinking rate, which may depend on the nutrient concentration, is included. In the model, there are no zooplanktons eating the algae. Instead a constant death rate, which also is assumed to include grazing, is included. Thus in this context, also zooplankton is included as a forcing variable. In addition to the eight prognostic variables already mentioned (DIA, FLA, NIT, PHO, SIL, DET, SIS and OXY), also light in the water column (RAD), and an inorganic suspended particulate matter variable (ISPM), are included (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: Schematics of the main biochemical variables and processes in NORWECOM.

The sedimentation/ resuspension of ISPM and DET is determined by critical values of the bottom stress determined by the modelled bottom currents and or effects from surface waves. Thus hind-cast surface wave fields provided by the Norwegian Meteorological

Institute is also used as forcing. Figure 19 demonstrates the biochemical variables and their interactions and links.

Initially the NORWECOM model did not have a particular harmful algae species as a state variable, just diatoms and flagellates as two functional groups. Therefore we cannot expect the model to predict where and when such a HAB will occur, and we are fully dependent on in situ and remote sensing data to initiate such a situation in the model. Within HABILE we improved the HAB-modelling capability of NORWECOM by introducing a third functional plankton group, representing the *Chattonella* spp.. In several occasions the first detection has been through death in fish farms leading to increased sampling and analysis of algae species. Sometimes HABs are detected by a Norwegian in situ monitoring program (27 coastal stations + ships + exchanging info with Sweden and Denmark) which is producing a weekly report called AlgeInfo (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>). Sometimes interesting features are found in the optical satellite images, and search for possible relevant in situ data is initiated. Unfortunately at present there are no algorithms for harmful algae detection from satellite data, which is a task reported in HABILE deliverable D.5. It is also unfortunate that our northern areas often have a cloud cover hiding the sea surface from being mapped by optical satellite remote sensing sensors.

When significant amounts of a harmful algae (high biomass) is detected, we make a best possible evaluation from satellite, in situ and modelled data on what area is covered and what the actual algae concentrations could be. The present day modelled fields of flagellates is “by hand” reinitialised to assumed concentrations (in future we aim at real assimilation of the EO data products), and then the model continue to predict the further development, advection and subsequent decay of the bloom. This method (preferably based on a good satellite coverage) seems to work for high biomass algae like the *Chattonella* being “similar” to our “average” flagellate. Repeated observations of the bloom are used for validation, and new re-initialisation will only be performed if the model is “way out”.

a) *The Chattonella HAB module*

The harmful *Chattonella* spp. has been modelled with a specially developed HAB module in NORWECOM. In every time step the concentration of *Chattonella* is updated according to:

$$\frac{\partial Cha}{\partial t} + adv(Cha) = diff(Cha) + P_{Cha} - R_{Cha} - D_{Cha} + \phi(Cha) \quad (1)$$

Here *adv* are the terms due to advection, *diff* the terms due to diffusion, *P* production, *R* respiration terms, *D* death and ϕ is sink and source terms due to sedimentation/resuspension and sinking (vertical migration) of the algae. Both the advection, diffusion and respiration terms are identical to those used for other phytoplankton, while the other terms are based on the *in situ* and laboratory findings as described above. In the HAB module the maximum production rate is set to 1.6X F(S,T), where F(S,T) a third order interpolation polynomial for the estimate growth rates (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Specific growth rate, *F*(Salinity, Temperature) for *Chattonella* (day⁻¹) (Naustvoll, unpul. data).

3.1.6 Model simulation results

a) The 2001 *Chattonella* bloom

For the *Chattonella* bloom in 2001 (see section 3.1.1, Figure 10) the NORWECOM model was used to simulate the bloom development and decay.

The first prediction up until the 28th of March (Figure 22- left) showed that the northeastward currents continued along the coast of Norway, keeping the algae from being transported around the southern to the western coast. In addition the algae were moved somewhat offshore in this region. At the same time the algae population at the Danish coasts were quite stationary. *In situ* observations from several places at the southwest and western coast showed little or no *Chattonella* (or other potential harmful species). Our prediction on the 21st of March for the following week was that *there is no threat of harmful algae to the fish farmers in western Norway during the coming week*. This was broadcasted on the radio and by several newspapers.

Figure 21: Modelled surface circulation and flagellate concentration on the 21st of March, 2001 with assimilated satellite observations (right) from the same day. Colours are not comparable since the model works on Carbon and the satellite in Chl-a units.

The 26th of March was the last day with nice weather and thus satellite information. As seen in Figure 10 there is a clear indication of reduction in the algal concentration. This is also indicated in the modelled image of the 28th (Figure 22).

Since in 2001 we did not have an operational system with daily reruns of the model, we only made a new prediction at the 29th of March for the following seven days. Still the abnormal circulation continued north-eastward along the Norwegian coast, while the algae on the west coast of Denmark progressed gradually into the southern Skagerrak. During this period up until the 5th of April, the model showed a significant decrease in flagellate concentrations (Figure 22) due to (modelled) nutrient limitations all over the Skagerrak. New *in situ* observations from several places at the southwest and western coast showed little or no *Chattonella* (or other potential harmful species), and observations from the southeastern coast indicated reduced concentrations of *Chattonella*. Our new prediction on the 29th of March for the following week was that: *there is no threat of harmful algae to the fish farmers in western Norway during the coming week, with clear indications of the Chattonella bloom coming to an end*. This was broadcasted on the TV and radio news and by several

newspapers. The first part of April was filled with bad weather, and with the predicted statement on the 29th of March of the bloom termination, the public interest of the bloom rapidly ceased as well as the concern of the aquaculture industry and fisheries authorities under impact of HAB events.

Figure 22: Modelled surface circulation and flagellate concentration on the 28th of March and 5th of April, 2001 with assimilated satellite observations from the 21st of March (see Figure 21).

This demonstrated a successful real time prediction of the development and decay of a HAB event. It was based on satellite and in situ detection of the bloom used for re-initialisation (assimilation) into the “average” flagellate compartment of the NORWECOM.

NORWECOM has also been used to simulate the onset and peak of the ecologically important spring bloom and its inter annual variations in space and time (Figure 23).

The model simulations may be off in time by a week or two, and this could clearly be improved by assimilation of satellite data. The limitation to this is cloudiness and the ability to separate the optical signal from chlorophyll *a* vs. the other optically active compounds in the water (mainly yellow substance) signal (see HABILE report D.5).

Figure 23: Modelled peak diatom production in 2000 (left), 2001 (right) and 2002 (under).

b) Inter annual simulations of *Chattonella*

NORWECOM model simulation using the developed and partly validated "HABILE *Chattonella*" module has been undertaken for the years 1999 to 2001. For all years the model initiate the bloom on set around day 100 (i.e. 85 to 125) and last for around one month (Figure 24 and Figure 25).

From these multi-year model simulations some limitations are identified. The first one is that the model indicates an extensive bloom in 1999, when no *Chattonella* bloom was observed. It is believed that the turbulent dependent death rate and the relatively strong winds in 1999 (see Figure 26) should be sufficient to stop the onset of a bloom, but this was not the case. The 1999 bloom starts during relatively calm (but short in duration) period on day 105. The intensity can be seen as the wind stress varies, with strong decline that coincides with the strong wind around day 120. This indicates that the mortality set in the model is still too weak to the growth rate.

From the observations the bloom in 1998 was about three weeks later than the one in 2000. This is also consistent with the records of the wind stress (Figure 26) that indicates a long calm period in 2000 from around day 100. In 2000 the model simulations give a first production maximum around day 105, then there is a decline before a new maximum is seen around day 120. In 1998 the peak production occurs around day 115, after a few days of almost no winds.

From the simulation studies several observations are drawn concerning the parameterization of *Chattonella* in NORWECOM. The first one is that there seems to be an imbalance between the maximum growth rate and the death rate. From observations we have no information of the death rate for *Chattonella*, except that the algae is removed when turbulence is added in the laboratory. Therefore, during strong wind events, there should be an almost immediate removal of *Chattonella* algae, such that the few algae produced during a few calm days will not initiate a bloom. The observed blooms have lasted for approximately one month, and there should be some kind of cut off in the death rate so that there will be no bloom unless periods of relatively calm weather occurs for periods of several weeks. From this the death rate should be exponential, and set after a close study of the modelled mixing values. During

HABILE we were not able to adjust the maximum growth rate vs. the formulation of the death rate. This is further complicated by the dependency of salinity and temperature on the growth rate (see Figure 20). Due to flooding in the rivers, there is a minimum salinity in the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) during the period March to May, and the increased salinity appears to be the reason for the blooms to stop in the model in May. Later in the season also the water temperature seem to be an efficient limitation for a second *Chattonella* bloom to occur. As the NORWECOM model is run with a horizontal resolution of 20 km (capable of resolving the important meso-scale variability), the circulation within Skagerrak is not very well resolved and the NCC are likely to be too wide and have too high salinity. Therefore it is necessary to operate a system of nested physical ocean model with resolution down to four kilometre in horizontal and better vertical resolution in order to be able to simulate the *Chattonella* blooms properly.

Figure 24: Annual depth integrated production of *Chattonella* for the years 1998 (upper left), 1999 (upper right), 2000 (lower left) and 2001 (lower right)

Figure 25: Figure 10: Time series of *Chattonella* production ($\text{gC}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$) outside Lista for the years 1998 (upper left), 1999 (upper right), 2000 (lower left) and 2001 (lower right)

Figure 26: Figure 6: Daily mean windstress (m^2s^{-2}) outside Lista in 1998 (upper left), 1999 (upper right), 2000 (lower left) and 2001 (lower right) for the period March-May.

3.2 Cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea

The cyanobacteria blooms are considered to be a natural phenomena for the Baltic Sea. The fossil records indicate the presence of cyanobacteria pigments dated back to 8000 years during the Litorina period of the Baltic Sea (Bianchi et al. 2000). However, recent plankton records indicate that the blooms of the nowadays common cyanobacteria species were rare before the World War II, although low number of cells were recorded (Finni et al. 2001). Since the 1960's, the cyanobacteria blooms have become common in the Baltic Sea.

The Baltic Sea is among the biggest brackish water seas with the salinity range from almost freshwater in the Bay of Bothnia to 15 psu in the Belt Sea, having also vertical stratification of salinity for instance from 7 at the surface to 11 psu at the bottom in the Baltic Proper. Salinity and temperature stratification especially during summers prevents the vertical mixing and input of inorganic nutrients from lower layers to the surface. Nutrient load has increased four-fold for nitrogen and eight-fold for phosphorus since 1900 (Larsson et al. 1985). The change of nutrient ratios seem to be the key factor in the evident change of phytoplankton species composition during the annual succession. These special features creates the the special features enabling the cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea.

Lots of scientific papers have been published about the limiting nutrient of the Baltic Sea, but there is no common conception of the limiting nutrient of pelagic production. Some authors claim phosphorus to be the most limiting (Eilola and Stigebrant 1999) but more common view prefer nitrogen (Bianchi et al. 2000, Tamminen 1985). According to nutrient enrichment experiments nitrogen deficiency seems to increase along the salinity gradient from the north to the south in the Baltic Sea (Hagström et al. 2001). Also in nutrient enrichment experiments only a combined inorganic N and P additions evoked an increase in algal biomass (Kivi et al. 1993, Lignell et al 2003).

Independent from the debate of the limiting nutrient conception a common concern is the intensified eutrophication. So the nitrogen fixing cyanobacteria can benefit from the conditions of low inorganic nitrogen. From that preconditions the potential cyanobacteria blooms can be predicted estimating the surplus phosphorus left over after spring bloom.

Accordingly the triggering factors for cyanobacteria bloom initiation in the Baltic Sea are summarized by:

Nodularia spumigena "Competitive exclusion of non-diazotrophs: surplus of dissolved phosphorous after the spring bloom, and low DIN < 0.1 µM/l. Stratified water column: calm weather. Wind speed < 5 m/s and high water temperature. > 15 °C during >1-2 weeks.

3.2.1 Field data analysis

The cyanobacteria occurrence in the Baltic Sea was evaluated according to the Alg@line data (for data description, see Ruokanen et al. 2003) for the years 1997-2002. The data for the most common species species *Nodularia spumigena* Mertens and *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae* Ralfs (further on referred as *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon*) were analysed. Many algal species can produce toxins in the Baltic Sea, but especially a real thread may cause frequent and wide blooms of the harmful cyanobacteria species *Nodularia* (Sipiä 2001, Laamanen 2001). Also frequently occurring cyanobacteria species *Aphanizomenon* is considered as a nuisance for fishing and recreation.

Although algal blooms, including toxic and harmful can be natural phenomena, the relationship between nutrient load, eutrophication and HABs is obvious. In September 1988 the Ministers of Environment of the Baltic States decided that anthropogenic nutrient load to the Baltic Sea should be reduced by 50% from year 1987 to 1995. In the follow-up evaluation (Lääne et al. 2002), the total point source loads of nitrogen and phosphorus decreased by 30 %, and 39 % respectively. However diffuse nitrogen loads from agriculture decreased only slightly, and decreases of phosphorus loads remained negligible.

Shifts in species composition have often been attributed to changes in inorganic nutrient supply ratios (Anderson et al 2002), as N:P, N:Si and also dissolved organic carbon to dissolved organic nitrogen (DOC:DON). High internal phosphorous storage in the cells is supposed to enable the cyanobacteria to grow even under limiting external phosphate concentrations. The blooms of *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia* decline after internal phosphorus depletion (Walve 2002). Also an increase of temperature in the summer, which lead to strong stratification seems to be the prerequisite for mass occurrence of *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia* (Figure 27).

Field data indicate that these cyanobacteria species have different demands on their environment: *Aphanizomenon* prefers lower temperatures and salinities than *Nodularia* (Figure 27, Figure 28). The different responses of *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon* may explain the different vertical, horizontal and temporal distribution of the two genera in the Baltic Sea. Both species are most abundant when the concentrations of dissolved inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus are low and also DIN:DIP-ratio is low (Figure 29 and Figure 30). Due to fixing of atmospheric nitrogen, they compete against phytoplankton whose growth rely on dissolved inorganic nitrogen.

Calm weather preceded by effective mixing seems to promote the development of cyanobacteria blooms. The formation of cyanobacteria blooms are favoured by warm and calm weather, while in cold and windy conditions other species formed mass occurrences. Water temperature and thus strong stratification has been found to be the main factor controlling the initiation of the bloom.

Figure 27: Occurrence of cyanobacteria in relation to temperature.

Figure 28: Occurrence of cyanobacteria in relation to salinity.

Figure 29: Occurrence of cyanobacteria in relation to phosphate concentrations.

Figure 30: Occurrence of cyanobacteria in relation to DIN:DIP ratio.

3.2.2 Seasonal and inter annual variability of the cyanobacteria blooms

Cyanobacteria take advantage of this situation through the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. The phosphorus-nitrogen ratio demonstrates the excess phosphorus available; usually yearly peaks occur after the spring bloom. That might be the period, when cyanobacteria start to accumulate inter cellular phosphorous for the growth later on. First, an increase of *Aphanizomenon* can be found with a maximum in the Gulf of Finland in June/July. As *Aphanizomenon* seems to be well adapted in low temperatures in contrast to *Nodularia*, higher abundances can be found already in spring. High temperatures in summer over 15°C cause an enhanced abundance of *Nodularia*, which is in few years reflected in the chlorophyll concentrations. Generally the chlorophyll a level tends to react to high abundance of total phosphorus, which is however not the case with cyanobacteria levels (Figure 29), which can be explained with intracellular storage of phosphorus.

The highest abundance of *Nodularia* in most years can be observed in the central Baltic Sea, where generally the highest sea surface temperatures occur. The growth of *Nodularia* decelerates when temperature decreases and results in a minimum abundance of *Nodularia* end of December. Low temperatures, decreasing solar radiation and enhanced mixing control the growth rate and keep a restricted phytoplankton stock in winter. Mineralization but mainly mixing lead to a replenishment of nutrients in the mixed layer depth in winter. In all years salinity shows no seasonal cycle.

Inter annual variability is reflected by differences in the time-dependent course of the individual parameters as well as their maximum. The highest inter annual variability occurs in the Gulf of Finland whereas fluctuations in the southern and central Baltic Sea are comparatively small. In both years 1997 and 1998 lower sea surface temperature and chlorophyll concentrations are observed in February compared to the years 1998-2002 in the three regions of the Baltic Sea. However, temperature increases rapidly in 1997 causing a fast growth of phytoplankton in spring and *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia* in summer.

The success of the frequently occurring harmful algal species *Nodularia* in the Baltic Sea seems to depend on the nutrient status after the spring bloom and summer weather conditions: - low N/P ratio (exhausted nitrogen) favours the growth of cyanobacteria and thus *Nodularia* as they can out compete phytoplankton by fixing atmospheric nitrogen - sufficient phosphate concentrations after the spring bloom can be preserved in their internal pools to consume them for growth under optimal conditions. - calm weather conditions - low wind and high temperatures- lead to a strong stratifications in summer which seems to be a prerequisite for the growth of *Nodularia*. Inter annual variability in atmospheric and thus physical but also chemical oceanic parameters are reflected by the growth development of *Nodularia*. However, whereas temperature directly affects the growth and thus the bloom development of *Nodularia* without time delay, variations in the phosphorous causes a smoothed and delayed response in *Nodularia* bloom development.

3.2.3 Modelling the cyanobacteria bloom in the Baltic Sea

Observations and the 1-D *phosphate concentrations* modelling studies indicate that advection (redistribution of temperature/salinity/nutrients) play an important role in the Baltic Sea. The evolution of sea surface temperature, up- and downwelling and mixed layer depth has to be taken into account as these parameters and processes directly (by temperature) or indirectly (by nutrient supply) affect cyanobacteria and phytoplankton growth and thus harmful algal bloom development.

The physical processes, which are involved in harmful algal bloom developments differs strongly from region to region. The semi-enclosed Baltic Sea is strongly influenced by freshwater inflow through river discharges and short-time wind-driven upwelling/downwelling events.

Within the cyanobacteria group, two main bloom-forming species occur, *Nodularia spumigena* (Mertens) and *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae* (Ralfs). Different hypotheses about the triggering factors controlling and stimulating the growth of harmful cyanobacteria have been suggested:

1. warm sea surface temperature and calm weather conditions favour the growth of harmful cyanobacteria. Whereas *Aphanizomenon* grows best in water temperatures about 12-17°C, *Nodularia* has its optimum temperature for growth at 12-25°C.
2. a low N/P ratio stimulates the growth of cyanobacteria and is even a precondition for cyanobacteria bloom development
3. increased availability of phosphorus by inflow of phosphor-rich water or release from sediment, initiate cyanobacteria blooms
4. salinity influences the occurrence of *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia*. *Aphanizomenon* can grow only in salinities below 10 psu whereas *Nodularia* can grow in water with salinities from about 3 to more than 30 psu.

The main features of the present FIMR HAB ecosystem model are described. A detailed description of the physical model and biological model can be found in Stipa (2002).

a) *Physical model*

The ocean model is the non-hydrostatic model based on the MIT GCM of Marshall et al. (1997) and has been configured for the Baltic Sea on a spherical polar grid with approximate 11 km * 11 km horizontal resolution and 21 vertical layers with increasing thickness with depth (for details, see HABILE deliverable D4).

For all tracers, a positive definite non-linear flux-limited advection scheme is taken. The sub-grid scale vertical turbulent transport of both oceanographic and biological tracers in our configuration is parametrized using the non-local KPP closure (Large et al, 1994).

b) *Ecosystem model*

A modified version of the biological model of Aksnes et al. (1995) has been coupled to the ocean model (Stipa, 2002). The model comprises the compartments phosphate, dissolved inorganic nitrogen and silicate as well as the phytoplankton groups diatoms and flagellates and the cyanobacteria *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon*. The fluxes between the compartments phytoplankton, cyanobacteria and nitrogen are computed in mM N m⁻³; the model includes also a prognostic silicate and phosphate compartment. Biochemical changes in the concentrations of the primary producers which comprise the phytoplankton group diatoms, flagellates and the cyanobacteria *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon*, are due to the actual growth rate, metabolic losses and mortality, which include the natural mortality as well as the grazing by zooplankton.

As the cyanobacteria are able to fix N₂, the growth of cyanobacteria does not depend on the concentrations of dissolved inorganic nitrogen, only the losses of the cyanobacteria go into the nitrogen pool. The uptake of phosphate depends on the growth rate of all primary producers and their metabolic losses. A fixed N/P ratio for the uptake and the metabolic losses of the primary producers is assumed as well as for silicate a fixed Si/N ratio for the uptake and growth of diatoms.

c) *Model coupling*

The biological model is coupled to the three-dimensional ocean model. The biological tracers are advected and diffused in the same way as the physical tracers at each time step.

d) *Initialization and Forcing*

The initial conditions for the physics and for the nutrients are derived from winter monitoring data, collected by the Finnish Institute of Marine Research in the period December 1999 to February 2000. The monitoring data have been supplemented by climatological values from the World Ocean Atlas. The primary producers are initialized with a vertical profile but horizontal homogeneously with winter values of 0.1 mM N m⁻³ at the surface. There is no difference in the initialization between the four functional groups. For the atmospheric forcing, the NCEP reanalysis data set (Kalnay et al., 1996) was taken: The ocean model was forced by surface fluxes of momentum, net precipitation and heat fluxes for the year 2000. The boundary conditions for the nutrients are derived from the MARE database.

3.2.4 Model Results

Nutrient concentrations in spring are relatively high and support the growth of phytoplankton. The simulated phytoplankton growth starts between March and April in the Baltic Sea, which is consistent with the data derived from the ship-of-opportunity (Alg@line): In agreement with these observations, the spring bloom propagates from south to north and from west to east in the Baltic Sea.

After the spring bloom dissolved inorganic nitrogen is almost exhausted and limits the growth of phytoplankton further on, whereas phosphate concentrations are still high. As a result the N/P-ratio decreases strongly after the spring bloom.

Although it has been proposed that cyanobacteria take up the phosphate which has been left over, simulation experiments show that the maximum of cyanobacteria biomass occurs about 60 days later than the minimum N/P-ratio which is consistent with observations (Figure 31). The model results, however, overestimates the increase of the N/P-ratio during the period of cyanobacteria growth which can be attributed either to missing remineralization or to the ability of cyanobacteria to take up dissolved inorganic phosphorus which is not included in the model, yet. This issue will be addressed in future. In agreement with observations, the time of the maximum cyanobacterial biomass and maximum temperature, however, coincide (Figure 32).

Figure 31: Time series of the N/P-ratio and cyanobacterial biomass (red) derived from observations within the Algaline project (left) and from simulations (right).

Figure 32: Time series of temperature and cyanobacterial biomass (red) derived from observations within the Algaline project (left) and from simulations (right).

The evolution of the cyanobacteria occurrences shows that the cyanobacterial maximum appears almost instantaneously in the whole Baltic Sea. As *Aphanizomenon* prefers lower temperature than *Nodularia*, the maximum biomass can be found app. 20 days earlier.

Moreover, *Aphanizomenon* builds up higher biomass than *Nodularia* in 2000. The highest concentrations of *Aphanizomenon* occur mainly at the Swedish coast and south of the entrance to the Gulf of Finland. The low concentrations of *Nodularia* in summer can be attributed to the low sea surface temperature, which has been also proposed by Moisander et al. (2002).

Figure 33: Time series of the *Nodularia* and vertical velocity.

Upwelling of cold water from below the pycnocline slows down the growth rate of *Nodularia* significantly (Figure 33), whereas in water, which is spread horizontally and heated before it is downwelled again, growth of *Nodularia* is enhanced. Whereas cold sea surface temperature favours the growth of *Aphanizomenon* in 2000 and slows down the growth of *Nodularia*, vice versa happens in the year 1999. Higher sea surface temperature favours the growth of *Nodularia*. The simulation experiment shows lower concentrations of *Aphanizomenon* compared to 2000 and also less biomass compared to *Nodularia*. High concentrations of *Nodularia* in 1999 occur maximum in the southern and central Baltic Sea and at the entrance to the Gulf of Finland.

In both years *Aphanizomenon* appears mainly at the Swedish coast and at southern part at the entrance to the Gulf of Finland. Striking are the low concentrations of *Nodularia* and *Aphanizomenon* in the Bothnian Bay which can be attributed to low phosphate concentrations. The low salinity in the Gulf of Finland due to the river inflow prevents *Nodularia* to build up high biomasses whereas high salinity in the Skagerrak is unfavourable for the growth of both cyanobacteria species.

a) Model simulations of outlook for summer 2004

Two scenarios for the development of cyanobacteria in the summer 2004 were derived in spring 2004. The monitoring results that were used to derive the indicators were used as initial conditions for the ecosystem model.

The modelled cyanobacterial scenarios were then combined with the empirical knowledge of Alg@line forecasters, and the results were given out to the media on May 7, 2004, as a best available forecast of HAB situation in the forthcoming summer.

Two scenarios for the development of cyanobacteria in the summer 2004 have been derived. The monitoring results that were used to derive the indicators of Figure 34 were used as initial conditions for the ecosystem model. The integration was performed with the atmospheric forcing for years 2000 and 2002, and the mean cyanobacterial biomass in the top 10 meters was analysed for the summer season (July-August; Figure 34).

Both scenarios show a high biomass for cyanobacteria in the Gulf of Finland area, with small variations in the north-south abundance distribution within the Gulf. The high level of the biomass is rooted in the high levels of phosphate, whereas the variation in the spatial distribution between the years is a symptom of the effect of the mean circulation regime on the mean cyanobacterial distribution in the Baltic Sea.

Despite the colder temperatures and consequently, the somewhat lower cyanobacterial biomasses in the northern Baltic, the cyanobacterial biomass was higher in the south-western Baltic in the 2000 scenario than in the 2002 scenario. This result appears to be caused by a sensitivity of the cyanobacterial blooms to weather conditions as opposed to

initial conditions (winter nutrient concentrations), which dominated the predictability in the Gulf of Finland for these scenarios for the 2004 conditions.

Figure 34: Two scenarios for the mean cyanobacterial biomass in the summer 2004. The scenarios are based on the initial condition in early February 2004 and the atmospheric development of the years 2000 (a cold summer) and 2002 (a warm summer).

The modelled cyanobacterial scenarios were combined with the empirical knowledge of Alg@line forecasters, and the results were disseminated as a press release to the media on May 7, 2004, representing the best available forecast of HAB risks in the forthcoming summer.

The same ecosystem model that was used in the 2004 scenarios and the 2000 validations were operationalized for 72 hours predictions for the summer 2004. In addition, the cyanobacterial abundance was intensely monitored by the Alg@line system. We followed the agreement between the monitoring and research results on the one hand, and the model results on the other hand several times a week. The summer 2004 turned out to be colder and rainier than the year 2000 was, and therefore an even more challenging growth environment for cyanobacteria. The phosphate concentration remained high and the cyanobacterial biomass low all the way to early July. Throughout the summer, most of the observed cyanobacterial biomass was found in the Alg@line observations in *Aphanizomenon*, which prefers the lower temperatures. In the daily model predictions, the *Aphanizomenon* biomass was consistently higher than *Nodularia* biomass throughout the summer. However, as the observed abundance of cyanobacteria is currently based in the Alg@line system on ranked cell counts that should be compared with the cellular concentration of nitrogen as predicted by the model, a quantitative comparison is currently not possible.

3.3 The Galician Rias

3.3.1 *Gymnodinium catenatum* blooms in the Galician Rias

Blooms of dinoflagellates, often harmful, are relatively frequent in the Rías Baixas of Galicia, four bays on the NW Iberian peninsula where seasonal upwelling-downwelling is one of the main oceanographic features (Blanton et al. 1984, Figueiras et al. 2002). The study of these blooms (Fraga et al. 1988, 1990, Figueiras et al. 1994, 1996, Fermín et al. 1996), especially recurrent at the end of the upwelling season (Figueiras & Ríos 1993), has provided a coherent picture for HABs dynamics in the region. Seasonal upwelling on the NW Iberian shelf occurs on average from March to September when northerly winds are dominant, whereas downwelling prevails during the rest of the year owing to the predominance of southerly and westerly winds (Figueiras et al. 2002). Coastal upwelling and downwelling greatly influence the circulation in the rías (Figure 35) and, therefore, the exchange processes between rías and the adjacent shelf (Álvarez-Salgado et al. 2000, Tilstone et al. 2000). Upwelling forces a two layers density-induced positive circulation in the rías, characterised by the outflow of surface waters and the compensating inflow of upwelled water at the bottom.

Figure 35: Schematic representation of circulation of the Ria during upwelling (a) and downwelling (b).

Transition to seasonal downwelling, which coincides with the rapid change to southerly winds, establishes a reversal circulation during which surface coastal water enters the rías to develop a downwelling front at the location where it meets the inner waters with higher continental influence. During this reversal circulation, the outflow towards the ocean in the outer circulation cell (Figure 35b) takes place at the bottom layer.

The reversal circulation modifies the distribution of microplankton assemblages along the rías and in the nearest shelf that, under upwelling conditions, is characterised by the dominance of diatoms in the inner waters and a higher importance of dinoflagellates towards the shelf (Tilstone et al. 1994). Downwelling causes the advection of dinoflagellates to the interior of the rías and promotes their accumulation in the downwelling front (Fraga et al. 1988, Figueiras et al. 1994, Fermín et al. 1996). This accumulation occurs because the vertical swimming capability of dinoflagellates allows them to compensate the downward velocity generated in this convergence. Diatoms, unable to counteract the downward velocity, are pushed down in the water column to be then exported towards the shelf by the bottom outflow (Figure 36).

This kind of HABs initiation has also been observed recently when a station on the shelf was monitored during a year with a sampling frequency of once a week (Figure 37). Consequently, it can be assumed that the autumn downwelling is the key oceanographic process for HABs initiation in the Galician region on the NW Iberian Peninsula.

Figure 36: Time evolution of (a) total microplankton and diatom abundance and (b) total microplankton and dinoflagellate abundance in the surface waters of a sampled station in the Ria de Vigo in 1987-88. Values in (a) and (b) are monthly averages. Vertical bars mark the autumn transition to downwelling.

Figure 37: Time evolution of temperature and mean abundance of diatoms, dinoflagellates and the swimmer species *Karenia mikimotoi* in shelf waters in front off the Ría de Vigo in 2001-2002. Vertical bars mark the autumn downwelling transition.

Regardless of the selection of dinoflagellates by downwelling, the actual development into a bloom also needs the appropriate nutrient supply, which takes place by the return of moderate upwelling conditions (Fermín et al. 1996, Figueiras et al. 1996), since strong upwelling enhances the positive circulation and favours diatom growth (Figure 38). High runoff during downwelling, other nutrient source for the surface layer, also enhances the positive circulation and, hence, the displacement of the downwelling front towards the shelf. Therefore, the two processes, strong upwelling and runoff tend to disperse dinoflagellates into the shelf waters.

Historical data also suggest that HAB episodes are related to long term variability in upwelling (Figure 39), which in turn is connected with North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO).

Upwelling relaxation

Downwelling

Downwelling relaxation-weak upwelling

Figure 38: Sequence showing the initiation and development of a *Gymnodinium catenatum* bloom in the Ría de Vigo in September-October 1993. Nitrate distribution can be used as a tracer of upwelling-downwelling

Figure 39: Graph showing the possible long-term relationship between climate variability and PSP events caused by *Gymnodinium catenatum* in the Galician Ría Baixas (NW Iberian Peninsula).

3.3.2 An ecosystem model for the Ría de Vigo

Since the upwelling seasonality is an important factor in the evolution of the Rías Baixas ecosystems and as dinoflagellates, which are the main responsible of HABs in the region, are normal components of the plankton community, a 3-D coupled hydrodynamic-ecosystem model was implemented for the Ría de Vigo.

a) *Model description of POLCOMS-ERSEM system*

The hydrodynamic component of POLCOMS-ERSEM is the three-dimensional baroclinic B-grid model described by Proctor and James (1996) and Holt and James (2001). It is a primitive equation finite difference model and a sophisticated advection scheme to minimise numerical diffusion and ensure the preservation of features even on coarse grids under oscillatory flows. Horizontal pressure gradients are calculated by interpolation onto horizontal planes. Turbulent viscosities and diffusivities are calculated using a Mellor-Yamada level 2.5 turbulence closure but with an algebraically specified mixing length. For a more detailed description of POLCOMS see D.4 and Holt and James (2001).

The ERSEM model is the same version to that described in the deliverable D.3. The food web included in the model (see D. 3 for more details) describes the carbon and nutrient pathways between functional groups of plankton. Both, particulate and dissolved organic matter are subdivided according to size and reactivity. ERSEM coupled to POLCOMS has been used in a variety of scenarios and domains (Allen et al., 2001, Holt et al., 2004).

b) *Forcing and model setup*

The model simulations were forced with 6 hourly European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) meteorological variables. ECMWF winds were applied only over the shelf domain while in situ wind measurements, freshwater inputs and cloud cover were applied to the domain inside the Ría de Vigo. No nutrient loading was included in the freshwater input under the assumption that the Ría's ecosystem dynamics are mostly driven by the upwelling/downwelling dynamics and the main nutrients source is bottom water from the shelf.

The model domain spanned an area between 42.055° and 42.382° N and -9.083° and -8.623° W. The western limit was the shelf and allowed upwelling and downwelling inside the ria. The domain size was 70x50 with a resolution of 1/150 of a degree or 750m x 550m. Sixteen vertical coordinate levels are used.

Boundary conditions of 15 tidal harmonics were used to drive the model, while T and S were interpolated from the Atlantic Shelf Wide 12km grid model run operationally by the MetOffice (<http://www.met-office.gov.uk/index.html>). No boundary conditions were used for ERSEM, which means it is run as a 1D model at the domain's boundaries. ERSEM was initialised from winter conditions and spun up for two years. The parameter set used for ERSEM is identical to the generic parameter set used in Blackford et al., (2004).

3.3.3 Model simulations results

The model seasonal response is characterised by the predominance of downwelling events in winter, with poleward shelf flow and enhanced stratification inside the Ría due to the high freshwater inflow. During the summer period (May-September) low river inflow is coupled with high solar insolation and upwelling winds, which maintains the stratification inside the Ría through advection from the shelf of saltier colder waters in the bottom layer.

The model reproduces both episodes of upwelling and downwelling showing a residual circulation in agreement with the current understanding of exchange processes between the Ría de Vigo and shelf (Souto et al., 2003). During periods of upwelling and southward circulation on the shelf, surface outflow takes place predominantly through the southern mouth (example from 3 April 2003, Figure 40a). Conversely, during downwelling conditions and northward shelf flow, the Ría outflow is mostly through the northern mouth (example from 3 May 2003, Figure 40b) and freshwater outflow is advected northward close to the coast. Although downwelling episodes do restrict Ría-shelf exchange, they rarely completely

reverse the surface circulation. This is also due to the few onshore winds episodes recorded during 2003, which might be different in other years.

Figure 40: Surface currents and salinity distribution during (a) an upwelling episode on 3 April 2003 and (b) downwelling on 3 May 2003.

The model also reproduces coastal upwelling in response to northerly winds on the shelf. Surface temperature decreases and nutrient levels increase close to the coast as bottom waters are advected inshore and surface near the coast. The two layer circulation of the ría (outflow in the surface and inflow in the bottom) is also well reproduced. Episodes of reversal circulation are reproduced during strong downwelling conditions.

Seasonal patterns of nutrient concentrations in the ría (e.g. Nogueira et al. 1997) are well represented by the model. The main source of nitrate and phosphate is bottom advection from the shelf during upwelling, while ammonia is generated in situ during weak upwelling. Overall, nutrient fields and dynamics are well reproduced in the model with the exception of silicate, which are 30% lower than expected. This suggests that river discharges can be other silicate source.

The variability seen in the nutrient fields in relation to the wind forcing (at short and seasonal time scale) is reflected in the phytoplankton biomass levels. The seasonal ecosystem dynamic (e.g. spring and autumn diatom bloom) is superimposed on to a shorter time scale wind driven dynamic. During active upwelling nutrients are advected into the Ría enabling sharp increases in primary production and phytoplankton biomass. Diatoms respond fastest although levels are lower than the field estimates presented in deliverable D.3 due to silicate limitation. Biomass partitioning across the ecosystem are comparable to estimates in D.3, the diatoms being the predominant group followed by flagellates and picoplankton. In the current implementation, dinoflagellates are the least successful functional group with biomass peaks of $< 10\text{mgC/m}^3$. Sensitivity analysis with the water column model (D3) indicated that the observed dinoflagellate peaks can only be simulated if the dinoflagellates are imported into the Ría from the open sea.

The effect of upwelling and downwelling episodes along the Ría de Vigo axis extending onto the shelf can be seen in Figure 41 and Figure 42. During upwelling episodes nutrient rich bottom shelf water is transported inshore (Figure 41a), fuelling production inside the Ría (Figure 41b). The reverse occurs during downwelling episodes; the two-layer circulation is weakened and at time reversed. Surface nutrient poor waters are advected inshore (e.g. nitrate Figure 42a) in turn reducing productivity (e.g. total chlorophyll Figure 42b).

Figure 41: Transect along the Ria's axis during an upwelling episode for (a) nitrate (mmol/m^3) and (b) total chlorophyll (mg/m^3).

Figure 42: Transect along the Ria's axis during a downwelling episode for (a) nitrate (mmol/m^3) and (b) total chlorophyll (mg/m^3).

Throughout 2003, net water flux across a N-S section at ST3 alternates between net export onto the shelf and net import into the Ria. This contrasts with the general net import of nitrate into the inner Ria. The constant decrease in ammonia flux into the Ria during the year reflects the increasing importance of *in situ* regeneration.

Phytoplankton biomass is generally exported from the Ria and only strong downwelling events (e.g. February) result in net biomass import. This suggests that a large proportion of the primary productivity inside the Ria is generated locally.

3.3.4 Scenario simulations of algal blooms in the Ría de Vigo

Five scenarios were prepared to assess the response of the system to changes in the freshwater nutrient loading and the wind drive upwelling. The scenarios are as follows;

1. Base Reference run with no river nutrients and realistic forcing.
2. NR (Nutrients in River) as base run, but with increased freshwater nutrient loading
3. NW (No Wind) as NR run, but with zero wind forcing across the domain.
4. HOF (High downwelling Frequency) as NR run, but with 3-7 days upwelling/downwelling cycles.
5. MUF (Moderate Upwelling Frequency) as NR run, but with 15-5 days upwelling/downwelling cycles.

a) Results - Effect of river nutrient loadings

The first scenario simulation involved the inclusion of constant nutrient loadings in the freshwater into the Ria de Vigo. Changes were measured in the year net integrated primary production (NIPP) in the NR run with respect to the base run throughout the domain (from 5 to 30% increase). The differences increase towards the inner Ria (Figure 43) and are larger than 10% throughout the Ria domain.

The annual average of N:P ratios changed only marginally between the two simulations. The largest differences being found in the inner Ria and constitute an increase from less than 12 to 14-15 representing a move towards the Redfield value of 16. A similar increase of 2 units was apparent in the MUF simulation with respect to the NR scenario.

Figure 43: Change in integrated net primary production from base simulation to simulation NR. Positive numbers represent an increase in production.

b) Results - Effect of Upwelling/downwelling cycles

Upwelling processes and freshwater inputs are the main nutrient sources into the Ria de Vigo. The impact of changes in the upwelling/downwelling cycle potentially have implications for the ecosystem dynamics from enhancing retention/export to increased nutrient supply with consequent shifts in the community composition. The largest impacts of these changes are likely to happen during the spring and summer period.

Consequently the wind forcing has been modified during the active upwelling period (May to September). Following Herrerea et al (submitted) artificial wind fields were modified by an across-shelf gradient of -10×10^{-3} and $28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ km}^{-1}$ in the U and V components. The simulations covered a broad range of integrated wind values from 0 (NW scenario) to predominant downwelling (HOF) or upwelling (MUF). Estimates of NIPP over the summer showed the largest production in the NR and MUF simulations (Figure 44b and d). The base and NW simulations (Figure 44a and c) were similar to each other and to the HOF simulation (not shown). Differences between NR and NW inside the Ria highlight the role of active upwelling in the nutrient supply to the Ria. The presence of wind during the summer of 2003 induced a 20% increase in production inside the Ria over the NW run. The periodic upwelling pulses in MUF were sufficient to enhance production inside the Ria over the NR simulation particularly in the innermost part.

Integration of the daily mean transport during summer (Table 2) showed an increase in water export with respect to the NR in NW and HOF simulations indicating weaker upwelling control on the dynamics. Transport of nutrients into the Ria decreased accordingly. At the same time, export of biomass decreased due to the reduced primary production. On the

other hand, the MUF simulation showed enhanced biomass export with respect to the NR run. Due to the cyclic nature of the forcing, there was a decrease in water export and a small increase in nitrate importation.

Figure 44: Net primary production for the summer period (May to September) for the a) base, b) NR, c) NW and d) MUF simulations.

Table 2: Percentage change of transport in and out of the Ria de Vigo with respect to NR simulation. Black font indicates changes in import while red indicates changes in export. In *italic* are increases while **bold** are decreases.

	NW	HOF	MUF
Total biomass	41% decrease export	52% decrease export	<i>2% increase export</i>
Water flux	<i>43% increase in export</i>	<i>83% increase in export</i>	52% decrease in export
Nitrate	31% decrease import	56% decrease in export	52% decrease export
Ammonia	55% decrease import	82% decrease import	62% decrease import
Silicate	60% decrease import	73% decrease import	28% decrease import.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the HABILE project environmental and biological data (*in situ* and satellite EO, both historical and newly acquired data) for three regional European marine ecosystems, all hampered by HAB events – i.e. the Baltic Sea, North Sea/Skagerrak and Galician Rias - have been analysed in order to identify the specific biological, chemical and/or physical HAB triggering factors.

Assessment and comparisons of data products from three different satellite Earth observation (EO) ocean colour sensors - SeaWiFS, MODIS and MERIS – have been undertaken. EO studies have been undertaken in order to study the inherent optical properties for development of new statistical methods for better discrimination HAB events in contrast to other algal blooms.

In order to investigate the optimal data assimilation parameterisation for HAB simulations twin experiments with a generic Ensemble Kalman Filter have been undertaken in order to utilize *in situ* and EO data sources in the ecosystem modelling. These conclude that nutrients assimilation performs well during well-mixed stratified conditions (winter), however phytoplankton biomass assimilation outperformed nutrients assimilation during the algae growth season.

Species specific information for the pre-dominant regional HAB species have been selected in order to parameterize and identify the key processes for the regional HAB triggering factors. These HAB parameterizations have been used to improve existing marine ecosystem models including algae modules. Scenario simulation studies have been performed for respectively the three geographical regional marine ecosystems in order to reproduce the bloom initiation, development and decay. Model conceptions have been developed respectively for cyanobacteria blooms (both the toxin producing *Nodularia spumigena* and *Aphanizomenon*) in the Baltic Sea, for the flagellate *Chattonella* spp. in the North Sea/Skagerrak region, as well as *Gymnodinium catenatum* for the Galician Rias.

Addressing the socio-economic impact of HAB events, a general methodology has been developed for *ex post* assessment studies taking into account the impact HAB events have in the various countries surrounding the European waters studied.

Several of the HABILE developed HAB monitoring and modelling tools will be further used in the on-going and future marine monitoring and modelling activities related to GMES, such as in the ESA GSE marine services, in the EC FP6 IP MERSEA and other national and international initiatives related to monitoring of HAB's in European waters.

The HABILE project has significantly improved the scientific foundation for the monitoring and prediction of HAB's hampering human activities in three major European coastal/marine ecosystems. During the project the four regional ecosystem models are in operation for respectively the North Sea/Skagerrak, The Baltic Sea and Galician Rias has been implemented, expanded and assessed with dedicated HAB modules. Monitoring and early warning methodologies for identification of possible HAB events have been developed and evaluated. Scenario ecosystem simulations had been done and impact assessments performed. The link to nutrient loads and balances for the HAB occurrences are drawn however the triggering factors also include the biological and physical initial and development conditions. The approach of an integrated monitoring, including *in situ* and satellite EO data sources, data assimilation tools and numerical model predictions are a requisite for efficient monitoring and forecasting of HAB events. The socio-economic impact of HAB has been studied and a methodology for its impact assessment suggested.

4.1 The Skagerrak North Sea

In the Skagerrak region *Chattonella* blooms are documented in three (1998, 2000 and 2001) of the seven years (1997-2002) studied in HABILE. The bloom dynamics within the three years show temporal as well as spatial differences. The first two blooms originated on the west coast of Jutland. The first bloom (1998) was transported to Norwegian and Swedish coastal waters by a combination of the Jutland current and the Baltic out-flow current. Most likely, the bloom was transported into the Swedish coast as a sub-surface bloom, and transported further north along the Swedish coast in intermediate depth. This circulation is “normal” for this region. Furthermore, there is evidence that the bloom was also transported directly from the Danish coast to the southern coast of Norway. Data from satellite images provides information on the spreading/advection of the bloom. The second bloom (2000) stayed mainly at the Danish West coast until it collapsed and disappeared. The third bloom (2001) was never observed at the west coast of Jutland and, most likely, originated in the Kattegat. From here it spread up north within the Baltic out-flow current. It seems likely that *Chattonella*, during the first two blooms had spread and established itself in the Kattegat area as a result of its ability to take over the pelagic environment following the diatom spring bloom. The blooms during the previous years might have provided a high inoculum for the secondary spring bloom of *Chattonella* in the area. Re-analysis of Swedish monitoring samples revealed that *Chattonella* did occur in non-bloom concentrations in the years before 1998. It is at present not clear whether the blooms were formed by one species/gender of *Chattonella* only or by several different species and if the species blooming in the years 1998, 2000 and 2001 is a new species to the area indeed.

The bloom dynamics of *Chattonella* at the Danish west coast indicate that in-situ growth is very important for the formation of the blooms. The spread of the bloom to the Swedish and Norwegian coastal waters is most likely a good example of advective down-stream long distance (several 100 kilometers) transport, which might have been maintained by additional *in situ* growth.

The present data also document that *Chattonella* is able to maintain itself in the upper meters of the water-column. Indicating that the swimming capability of *Chattonella* in combination to the swimming behaviour is of major importance to bloom formation and maintenance.

Unfortunately, information on the abundance of potential grazers, such as microzooplankton and mesozooplankton on *Chattonella* and other naked flagellates, are not available for the research area. It is most likely that differences in grazing pressure between the years, during the initial growth phase, can be important in determining whether a bloom was formed or not.

The biological observations on the *Chattonella* bloom and non-bloom situations are backed up by detailed monitoring information on the physical and chemical oceanography of the environmental conditions before, during and after the blooms. The information not only covers the surface waters in detail, but also includes detailed information on the vertical structure of the water masses.

Once *Chattonella* is present in the water masses, by transport from other region, as a result of germinations of benthic resting cysts, or vegetative growth, the physical and chemical condition, as well as biological factors, are important for the development of a bloom. The time lag from the species is present in a pelagic water mass until it can build up a high biomass bloom is approximately 3-4 weeks. This highlights the importance of pre-bloom monitoring data for analyses of bloom development and dynamics.

It is most likely that the run-off of inorganic nutrients to the coastal waters of the *Chattonella* bloom area is sufficient to satisfy the demand of *Chattonella* in all the years during the period 1997-2002. However, several basic physical assumptions must be fulfilled for the *Chattonella* bloom formation to take place. The physical setting must include distinct water masses with available inorganic nutrients such as the Jutland water mass in the shallow part of the coastal North Sea or the water mass within the stratified Baltic out-flow current running up north the Swedish west coast with a pycnocline at 5-15 m depth, into the coastal waters of southern Norway. The combination of a physical distinct water mass and injection of inorganic nutrients from land assures that in-situ growth can take place in a nutrient rich

environment and that the cells produced will not be dispersed into the neighbouring waters. The presence of the physical features such as the Jutland Current and the Baltic outflow current are of major importance for the spread/advection of the bloom in the region. The dynamics of the Jutland current and the Baltic out-flow current are controlled by the meteorological (wind) conditions.

Bloom development needs the following environmental conditions to be fulfilled:

- Sufficient light (time window: March-May)
- Temperature exceeding threshold for growth (time window: March-May)
- Salinity within the range which allows for high growth rates (time window: March-May)
- Existence of a distinct coastal water mass/plume e.g. The “Jutland Current” which needs calm weather to form, to prevent dispersion of the bloom in-to the North Sea
- Excess nutrients, which will exist in the case where a distinct coastal water mass/plume is present. The Jutland current contains high loads of N, P and Si originating from the major NW European continental rivers such as the river Elbe.

Biological/ecological conditions of importance:

- Sufficient initial population “seeding” population size in February/April which is dependent upon bloom extent in previous year as well as advected transport of populations from down-stream the bloom area
- Low grazing rate

Bloom maintenance:

- Calm weather to prevent dispersion of the bloom
- A coastal circulation that will concentrate the population in the coastal plume
- Low grazing pressure
- Nutrient availability to accommodate on going in-situ growth

Bloom crash/disappearance:

- High wind speed to disperse the bloom
- Advection out of the initial bloom area
- Nutrient depletion – causing mortality/sedimentation
- High mortality rate
- Encystment processes (not studied in HABILE)

The proposed bloom scenarios were simulated using 3D modelling using the model NORWECOM. The model successfully simulated the advection of the blooms and to a certain extent also the timing and geographical distribution of the blooms. During the 2001 bloom a combination of satellite and in-situ detection of the bloom used for re-initialisation (assimilation) into the “average” flagellate compartment of the NORWECOM, provided useful real-time time prediction of the bloom development and decay of the bloom.

In the case of *Chattonella* the 1-D modelling exercises demonstrated the environmental circumstances under which a bloom may occur. These types of simulation are useful in that they demonstrate how environmental conditions and biological interactions interact and tentatively support hypotheses about the controlling factors on HAB blooms.

However, parameter uncertainty will probably prevent them from having a useful predictive function. Model uncertainty is inevitable and a consequence of the limitations of the model structure, parameterisations and data. This indicates the need for appropriate physiological information to define and parameterize such models and data to validate them.

The HABILE results supports the needs for integrated monitoring taking the full advantage of using and developing satellite EO observational techniques, in situ a and ships of opportunity monitoring as well as numerical simulation prediction models. The models can favourably be tuned through re-initialization or more advance assimilation of observational data as appropriate and available.

4.2 The Baltic Sea

For the cyanobacteria blooms in the Baltic Sea the HABILE project has made results from simulation experiments with a 3D-coupled biological-ocean model. The biological model includes two cyanobacteria species - *Aphanizomenon* and the toxin-producing species *Nodularia*. The main findings of the HABILE studies includes:

- at the beginning of the growth of both cyanobacteria, low concentrations of dissolved inorganic nitrogen limits the growth of phytoplankton
- time delay between the minimum N/P-ratio and maximum cyanobacteria biomass
- model underestimates phosphate concentrations and thus overestimates the N/P-ratio during the growth of cyanobacteria
- the growth of cyanobacteria species starts in summer when sea surface temperature are rising
- time of maximum biomass of cyanobacteria coincide with maximum temperature
- the maximum of both cyanobacteria occurs almost instantaneously in the whole Baltic Sea
- *Aphanizomenon* appears about 20 days earlier than *Nodularia*
- *Nodularia* is sensitive to cold sea surface temperature and can be thus found rather at downwelling spots
- cold summer sea surface temperature in 2000 prevent *Nodularia* from blooming whereas growth of *Aphanizomenon* is enhanced
- in 1999 *Nodularia* biomass is higher compared to 2000 and to *Aphanizomenon* due to higher sea surface temperature
- Model forecasts show the tendencies of cyanobacteria development but the weather conditions development creates the uncertainties for the forecasts.

4.3 The Galician Rias

The HABILE project hypothesise that the triggering factors of harmful dinoflagellate initiation in the Galician Rías Baixas is the coincidence of downwelling with low runoff (coastal downwelling: runoff ratio ≥ 7) during the autumn season, when dinoflagellates are present in the microplankton community. Downwelling excludes diatoms from the competition for nutrients. Bloom development needs the return to weak upwelling conditions, which then supply nutrients for dinoflagellate growth.

To explore this hypothesis we have implemented of POLCOMS-ERSEM in the Ria de Vigo. The model successfully reproduces the main physical dynamics of the region, simulating both upwelling and downwelling processes and the ecosystem response at the seasonal and short time scale. The model fields are in agreement with *in situ* measurements. The pelagic ecosystem community structure resembles *in situ* measurements although diatoms are underrepresented due to the low silicate present in the model. Over the simulated year, the Ria showed on average a net export of biomass and a net import of nutrients.

To explore the sensitivity of this system we have looked five scenario simulations describing the response of the pelagic ecosystem to changes in the forcing fields like river nutrient loadings and upwelling/downwelling wind cycles for the Galician Ria. We have presented five scenario simulations describing the response of the pelagic ecosystem to changes in the forcing fields like river nutrient loadings and upwelling/downwelling wind cycles for the Galician Ria.

We find the model Ria constantly exports the biomass produced inside it. Upwelling mediated nutrient fertilization of the Ria is very important, in particular during the spring and summer. However, the effect of river nutrients also produces important changes to the pelagic ecosystem. It is the coupling of the two fertilization paths, which generated the highest integrated production. Only short-lived strong downwelling winds caused biomass from the shelf to accumulate inside the Ria, thus supporting our initial hypothesis.

Additionally the simulations indicate that while there were changes to summer integrated N to P ratios in the different scenarios, they were small and unlikely to produce large shifts in the phytoplankton community composition.

5 DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF THE RESULTS

Under HABILE four peer-review articles have been published during the course of the project. Furthermore two papers have been accepted for publication and four are under review (May 2005). One book contribution has been accepted for publication. Additionally 10 peer-review papers are under preparation for submission and eventual publication during 2005. One book "*Monitoring of Harmful Algae Blooms - The contribution by remote sensing*" is under preparation to be published by Springer-Praxis.

HABILE project results have been presented orally or as posters at about 30 relevant scientific and managerial conferences, most with proceedings of papers or extended abstracts.

A project web-site has been established and maintained under the project - <http://www.nersc.no/HABILE/>.

Subsequent regional HAB monitoring efforts are disseminated to the public and users communities following directly the HABILE project are found at <http://HAB.nersc.no> for the North Sea and Skagerrak region and coastal Norwegian waters, at <http://balticseaportal.fi> for the Baltic Sea and at <http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsg/projects/mceis> for the UK/Irish waters.

The R&D results of HABILE are directly applicable in the European efforts under the EC and ESA initiatives to GMES (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security). The ESA GMES Service Element (GSE) addresses specifically HAB monitoring as one element of marine services to be implemented for all European waters. Both the HABILE achievements in improvements of use of satellite Earth observations for early identification and monitoring as well as the modelling and assimilations of data for improved predictions of HAB occurrences are both essential components in the implementation of operational marine service elements of GMES at a European level by 2008. In this respect the HABILE results will be further utilized and developed in the FP6 MERSEA IP and in the ESA GMES Service Element (GSE) to be implemented by 2008.

HABILE results can be further exploited in e.g. "The Oceans" initiative under FP7.

5.1.1 ESA GMES Service Element (GSE): Phase 2 – the MARCOAST Proposal

NERSC was one prime service provider for Harmful Algae Bloom monitoring in the ROSES (Real-time Ocean Services for Environment and Security) project under ESA GMSE Service Element - Phase 1 (2003 – 2004). Alcatel Space coordinated the ROSES services. The primary objective of ROSES was to deliver an operational and autonomous European capacity and services for global monitoring for marine environment and safety. This will be achieved as part of the GSE to establish the scope and roles for the development of Earth Observation applications. NERSC delivered HAB monitoring and forecasting products in near real-time for the North Sea region (<http://HAB.nersc.no>) under the ROSES project.

The ESA GMES Service Element Phase 2 Invitation to tender is currently under evaluation. The marine service elements of GSE (including HAB alert services and water quality monitoring) are submitted in the MARCOAST tender, lead by Alcatel Space. This proposal is currently under review with ESA.

NERSC was invited in MARCOSAT to be responsible to the "Algae Bloom Alert monitoring and modelling" as well as the "Water quality monitoring" WP's for the northern North Sea/Skagerrak and the Norwegian Coastal Current waters. These tasks will include the further use of HABILE satellite EO monitoring results and modelling tools. These activities will be coordinated with related national activities

PML is involved in two of the proposed workpackages for the MARCOAST project to monitor the European marine environment: Water Quality Monitoring, and Algae Bloom Alerts.

FIMR was invited to the MARCOSAT "extensions" for the Baltic Sea.

5.1.2 Norwegian activities – “SatHav” and “Havet og Kysten”

The Norwegian Space Centre is implementing a national program for implementation of marine services for monitoring of coastal and marine waters of Norwegian interest. The HABILIE methodologies for use of EO data and HAB modelling will be further used in this program. These activities will be coordinated with the national involvement in the marine parts of GSE.

The HABILIE results will form a good basis for the further marine ecosystem research planned in Norway under program “Havet og Kysten” (“Oceans and the Coast”) to be implemented from 2006 by the Research Council of Norway. The Norwegian partners will in this respect make a joint applications to this program.

HABILIE project and cooperation has also contributed to strengthen the international exchange of information between the “Scandinavian” countries all monitoring coastal waters of common interest.

5.1.3 Marine and Coastal Environment Information Services (MCEIS) - UK

The Marine and Coastal Environment Information Services (MCEIS) project was a 6 month project (October 2004 – March 2005) supported under the British National Space Centre (BNSC), European Ministerial Preparatory Action (EMPA) programme.

Following recent environmental policy initiatives and agreements, such as OSPAR and the Water Framework Directive, government agencies now have a legislative requirement to provide water quality monitoring services. MCEIS bought together key UK organisations to develop and deliver a pilot water quality monitoring service, based on a combination of satellite, model and in situ data. The UK user agencies (EA, CEFAS, FRS, SEPA, EHS) have reviewed these services and contributed to a final report, which provides recommendations for operational implementation, as required to satisfy UK agencies’ long-term requirements. Plans for implementation include participation in the MARCOAST proposal for marine environment monitoring services under the European Space Agency’s GMES Service Element programme.

MCEIS exploited HABILIE’s results in the form of MODIS near-real time processing, and automated classification of certain HAB species from SeaWiFS data.

From October 2004 delivered a pilot water quality service covering the entire coastline of Britain and Ireland, at <http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsg/projects/mceis>, providing:

- Near Real Time processed satellite data (updated daily, and weekly composites)
 - ✓ Chlorophyll, water clarity and suspended particulates
 - ✓ Sea-surface temperature
- Near Real Time Model Fields
 - ✓ Surface and bottom temperature and currents from the POL Irish Sea model (1.8km resolution).
- In Situ Data
 - ✓ CEFAS SmartBuoy Data (fluorescence, PAR irradiance, salinity, temperature and turbidity)
- Functionality
 - ✓ Individual images can be viewed interactively.
 - ✓ Functions include zooming, interactive colour scale, selection of coastline overlays.
 - ✓ Equivalent processed images produced by different satellites can be compared side-by-side
 - ✓ A searchable online archive.
- Following user feedback these services were upgraded to include
 - ✓ Time series of EO and model derived water quality statistics at selected sites,
 - ✓ Archived output from UK Met Office Medium Resolution (6km) Continental Shelf coupled bio-geophysical model.
- Carried out a full service evaluation, developed recommendations for development & exploitation.
 - ✓ Users have identified priorities are to provide statistics of EO and model derived water quality indicators aggregated either onto a regular grid, or mapped onto WFD or OSPAR assessment regions, and the development of a warning system to advise of potentially harmful events (e.g. Harmful Algal Blooms).

Algal bloom alerts: The MCEIS team, with the Finnish Institute of Marine Research (FIMR), have proposed an Algae Bloom alert and forecasting Extension service for UK and Baltic

waters. The “UK Group” will offer EO and model derived HAB warning and advice, backed up by near real time in situ data from buoys and ferrybox routes. These services will cover the Great Britain and Ireland coastline.

5.1.4 UK National Water Quality Service

There is a proposal underway to extend the MCEIS pilot project into a national UK service to deliver water quality products and HAB alerts. This may provide additional developments to that of the ESA MARCOAST project, described above.

The UK user agencies have expressed an interest to maintain MCEIS as an operational service. A specific recommendation from FRS was that an operational (and sustainable) basic monitoring service (using EO data and model output) be established as soon as possible, with developments and refinements to be added in progressively.

We are hopeful that the ESA GSE programme may provide some medium term support, but it is clear that complementary activities are necessary to ensure a useful operational service is implemented.

We propose an implementation plan for a national EO and model based water quality monitoring service, building upon the existing MCEIS capability. This proposal is intended to be complementary to plans being developed within DEFRA, IACMST and elsewhere, providing a practical first step on the way to a possible wider national facility.

5.1.5 Socio-economic relevance, strategic aspects and policy implications

a) *The Baltic Sea*

The cyanobacteria blooms are the main HAB blooms in The Baltic Sea. The two main bloom forming and nitrogen fixing cyanobacteria are *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae* and *Nodularia spumigena* during the whole growth season in the Baltic Sea. Blooms of cyanobacteria are associated with higher concentrations of phosphate in relation to inorganic nitrogen. In addition, weather conditions especially water temperature and wind regime has an effect on bloom formation.

Initiatives to reduce loads of phosphate and nitrogen into sea water are the key to reduce cyanobacterial biomass. In addition, initiatives to decelerate global warming ought to be strengthened in order to reduce cyanobacteria bloom intensity and duration.

Participation in HABILE project has enabled the development of the [Alg@line](#) consortium project (<http://balticseaportal.fi>) for HAB monitoring in the Baltic Sea. Especially during the project satellite data validation for monitoring of phytoplankton and HAB blooms has been developed. Also the sql database for [Alg@line](#) data has been developed (together with other financial sources). Ecosystem and algal bloom modelling has taken a step forward and is in operational service nowadays. (<http://www.fimr.fi/en/itamerinyt/ekomallit.html>).

The HAB monitoring development in FIMR during the HABILE project made it possible for FIMR to propose services to ESA Earthwatch GMES elements, stage 2. The proposed services are included in the Marine and Coastal environmental services (MARCOAST) for Water quality, HAB alert, HAB evolution and forecast. GMES services are planned to start in the autumn 2005.

Dissemination and exploitation of the results both during and post project: The operational HAB monitoring and alert information is disseminated in the first hand through the Baltic Sea portal web page (<http://balticseaportal.fi>) The further analysed statistical phytoplankton and HAB data are published in HELCOM fact sheets (Kaitala 2004, Fleming 2004)¹, and in EUROGOOS 2005 conference and in international conferences of remote sensing during 2005.

¹ Kaitala S, Laamanen M, Hällfors S, Hällfors H (2004) Helcom Indicator Fact Sheet 2004: Cyanobacteria bloom index.

http://helcom.navigo.fi/environment/indicators2004/cyanobacteriaindex/en_GB/index/

Fleming V., Kaitala S. 2004: HELCOM Indicator Fact Sheet 2004. Phytoplankton spring bloom biomass in the Gulf of Finland, Northern Baltic Proper and Arkona Basin in 2004.

http://helcom.navigo.fi/environment/indicators2004/cyanobacteriaindex/en_GB/estimates

b) *The Galician Rias*

The Rías Baixas of Galicia on the Northwest Iberian Peninsula support the highest of Europe and one of the world most intensive mussel production. The region suffers from frequent HAB episodes that disrupt the mussel harvest having important socio-economic consequences. Since mussel production alone gives employment to 9,000 people directly and to 20,000 people indirectly, research on oceanographic processes underlying HAB development have deserved continuous effort. In this context, historical and recently collected data have been analysed within the HABILE project with the aim of establishing possible correspondences between oceanographic processes-structures and HABs in the Galician Rias. These analyses allowed recognise that microplankton species causing HABs belong to the normal microplankton constituents of the region and that coastal downwelling is the oceanographic process that triggers off their proliferation.

All the collected information has been analysed and used to implement, for the first time in the region, a physical-biological coupled model that, without doubt, constitutes a very useful tool for the understanding of HAB initiation, development and decay. With this model the simulation of different scenarios will be possible and the influence that human induced environmental changes could have on HABs would be assessed in the next future. Thus, HABs variability could be analysed in the perspective of climate change and enhanced eutrophication, among other possible environmental changes. Consequently, the anticipation of the effects that these changes could have on HABs, through enhancing their intensity or frequency, would be achievable. In this way, HABILE has improved our understanding of HABs in the Rías Baixas considerably and has also supplied a tool that, throughout a better understanding of the processes conducting to HAB development, would promote a more efficient management of the decisions taken to minimise risks and effects of HABs. In this aspect and since HABs are natural phenomena, the anticipation of the probability of HAB occurrence appears as a very useful output of the model. This would permit to manage mussel cultures adequately.

5.1.6 Further socio-economic impact studies

The Socio-economic Impacts of HABs in European Waters performed under HABILE has given two important results, respectively a classification and measuring of different socio-economic effects caused by HABs, and the statistical material indicates that the frequency of HABs and the socio-economic losses have increased during the last 15 years. Increased frequency of HABs emphasizes not only the importance of monitoring and registering of HABs, but also the need for furthering the analysis of causes to HABs and effects, and relevant means for reducing or stabilizing poisoning alga blooms.

Following up the HABILE project two exploitation activities are explicitly identified by NERSC and SNF;

I. *Harmonization of monitoring strategies at a European level:* Most countries monitor and register HABs, but there is no systematic attempt to estimate the socio-economic effects. The Directorate of Fisheries in Norway registers (in numbers of individuals) losses in the aquaculture industry caused by jellyfish and HABs, but they do not estimate the losses in economic terms. This is the situation in many countries. In a furthering of the project we will cooperate with the Directorate of Fisheries and the aquaculture industry to collect relevant HAB-data and make it possible to estimate the socio-economic impacts of HABs. We will present the methodology, among other factors the accountant table for HAB-events (see project report D.10), to the administrative body. We will arrange a seminar/workshop where researchers can present results from among others the HABILE-project. One of the objectives in this part of the project will be to establish contact with the relevant industries and administrative bodies and implement in practical action the results obtained from the HABILE project.

II. *Analysis of the causes to HABs and relevant policy instruments:* This is an interdisciplinary project. In furthering the project we regard it as important to analyze the causes behind the seemingly increasing frequency of HABs in European waters. There exists different hypothesizes which explain the evolvement of HABs, for example increased pollution (runoff), spread of alien organism with ballast water and climate change. In that respect frequencies of HABs give information about the health condition of the ecosystem. Some of

the causes to HABs are analyzed in the HABILE-project but mainly on microbiological level. A lot of data are collected during the HABILE project, but it is not carried out any statistical analyses between HABs and biological and oceanographic variables – also on macro-data-level. One important scientific objective is to carry out statistical analyses, aiming at causal-effect analysis of HABs. Based on this it is possible to discuss which policy instruments are realistic and efficient to apply in an attempt to reduce the societal negative impacts of HABs in Europe.

6 MAIN LITERATURE PRODUCED

6.1 Published Peer Review Articles

Authors	Title	Journal	Volume
Nogueira, E., F.G. Figueiras	The microplankton succession in the Ría de Vigo revisited: species assemblages and the role of the weather-induced, hydrodynamic variability.	Journal of Marine Systems	54 (2005): pp.139-155.
Allen, J.I., Siddorn, J.R., Blackford, J.C., Gilbert, F.J.	Turbulence as a control on the microbial loop in a temperate seasonally stratified Marine Ecosystem.	Journal of Sea Research	52(1), 2004, pp. 1-20
Shutler, J.D., T.J. Smyth, P.E. Land, and S.B. Groom,	A near real-time automatic MODIS data processing system.	International Journal of Remote Sensing	26 (2005), No. 5, pp 1049-1055
Pulliaainen J., Vepsäläinen J., Kaitala S., Hallikainen M. Kallio, K., Fleming V. and Maunula P.	Regional Water Quality Mapping through the Assimilation of Space-Borne Remote Sensing Data to Ship-Based transect Observations.	J. of Geophysical Research.	109, C12009: 1:11.

6.2 Non refereed literature/communication

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type ²
Pettersson, Lasse H.	2002	Satellite data and ocean models for monitoring of HAB – useful tools for aquaculture industry and fisheries authorities (in Norwegian)	Journal	Aquatic no. 4	Paper
Lars J. Natvik	July 2003	Ecosystem models based on hybrid vertical coordinates.		no. 241	NERSC technical report
Douding, L., Göbel, J., Hetscher, M., Horstmann, U., Davidov, A.	2003	Detection of noval algal blooms of Raphidophytes in the Eastern North sea with satellite images of MOS and SeaWiFS	Proceeding of SPIE	Vol. 4892, pp 116-122, 2003.	Paper
Miller, P., G. Moore, and S. Groom	2003	SeaWiFS discrimination of harmful algal blooms	Sensing and Mapping the Marine Environment from Near and Far, London	CSMS and RSPSoc Symposium	Abstract
Miller, P., G. Moore, J. Shutler, and S. Groom	2003	SeaWiFS discrimination of harmful algal blooms	The Impact of Satellite Technology on Maritime Security, Vigo, Spain	EURISY Conference Proceedings, pp. 24,	Abstract
Miller, P., G. Moore, J. Shutler, and S. Groom	2003	SeaWiFS discrimination of harmful algal blooms	Scales and Dynamics in Observing the Environment, Nottingham, UK	Proceedings of Annual Conference of the Remote Sensing and	Abstract

² Type: Abstract, Newsletter, Oral Presentation, Paper, Poster, Proceedings, Report, Thesis

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type ²
				Photogrammetry Society	
Pulliainen J., Vepsäläinen J., Kaitala S., Koponen S., Kallio K., Rantajärvi E., Kiirikki M.	August 24-28, 2003.	Assessment of water quality in the Baltic Sea through the use of satellite remote sensing observations.	The Baltic Sea Science Congress 2003 Helsinki, Finland,		Abstract
Kaitala S., Rantajärvi E., Fleming V.	August 28-29, 2003	Annual succession of chl-a in different areas of Baltic Sea according to Alg@line measurements.	Remote sensing and bio-optical modelling of the Baltic Sea. 2 nd international workshop, Helsinki.	The Baltic Sea Science Congress 2003 Helsinki, Finland	Abstract
Pulliainen J., Vepsäläinen J., Kaitala S., Kallio K., Rantajärvi E., Koponen S.	August 28-29, 2003	Assimilation of satellite data with Alga@line ship-of-opportunity observations in the spatial chlorophyll concentration retrieval	Remote sensing and bio-optical modelling of the Baltic Sea. 2 nd international workshop, Helsinki.	The Baltic Sea Science Congress 2003 Helsinki, Finland	Abstract
Vepsäläinen J., Kaitala S., Pulliainen J., Kallio K., Rantajärvi E.	August 28-29, 2003	The synergy of MODIS and SeaWiFS data and unattended flow-through fluorometer measurements.	Remote sensing and bio-optical modelling of the Baltic Sea. 2 nd international workshop, Helsinki.	The Baltic Sea Science Congress 2003 Helsinki, Finland	Abstract
Pulliainen, J., Jenni Vepsäläinen, Seppo Kaitala, Kari Kallio, Eija Rantajärvi, and Sampsa Koponen	24-27 September, 2003	Spatial mapping of chlorophyll concentration in the Baltic Sea through the assimilation of satellite data with ship-of-opportunity observations.	ICES Annual Science Conference, Tallinn, Estonia.	ICES Proceeding	Abstract
Totti Takio, Jenni Vepsäläinen, Seppo Kaitala and Vivi Fleming	24-27 September, 2003	Remote sensing of chlorophyll a in the Baltic Sea together with automated fluorometer measurements	ICES Annual Science Conference, Tallinn, Estonia.	ICES Proceeding	Paper
Krawczyk, H., Ebert, K.	10-13 November 2003	Detection of Algae-blooms in the Baltic Sea with MERIS-data	MERIS User Workshop, Frascati, Italy	ESA proceedings	Paper
Groom, S., P. Miller, and J. Shutler	2004	Remote sensing of harmful algal blooms: near-real time monitoring and bloom discrimination	Operational Oceanography and Remote Sensing	Alliance for Marine Remote Sensing (AMRS) Conference 2004	Invited talk
B. Karlson	17-18 February, 2004	Results from EU-project HABILE.	Meeting with the information offices for the Bothnian Bay, Baltic Proper and the Skagerrak and the Kattegat, Gothenburg, Sweden.	-	Oral presentation
Neumann, A., Krawczyk, H., Borg, E., Fichtelmann, B.	26.-28. April 2004	Towards Operational Monitoring of the Baltic Sea by Remote Sensing	BaltCoast Conference, Rostock-Warnemuende, Germany	Proceedings	on-line version

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type ²
Hense I., Kaitala S., Stipa, T. (2004)	26. - 29. April 2004.	Phosphate uptake behaviour of cyanobacteria.	Open Science Meeting on the Core Research. Project: HABs in fjords and coastal embayments. Vina del Mar, Chile	GEOHAB	Abstract and Poster
Ebert, K., Krawczyk, H., Neumann A.	14.-17. June 2004	"Interpretation of satellite remote sensing data in the Baltic Sea with special respect to Harmful Algae Bloom events".	U.S.-Baltic International Symposium, Klaipeda, Lithuania,	Proceedings	Paper
Ebert, K.	15-27 August 2004,	"Ocean-Colour Remote Sensing with special respect to algal bloom detection"	2 nd ENVISAT summer school, Frascati, Italy	ESA Proceedings	Poster Paper on-line
Folkestad, A., L.H. Pettersson, and D. Durand	Sept., 2004	Ocean colour multi-sensor analysis during a phytoplankton spring bloom in the North Sea region.	ENVISAT & ERS Symposium, Salzburg, Austria	ESA proceedings	Paper
Folkestad, A., L.H. Pettersson, and D. Durand	Sept., 2004	Inter-comparison of ocean colour data products during algal blooms in the North Sea.	ENVISAT & ERS Symposium, Salzburg, Austria	ESA proceedings	Paper
B. Karlson	November, 8-9, 2004	Presentation of results from EU-projects HABES and HABILE.	Global Monitoring for the Environment and Security (GMES) seminar, Brussels, Belgium.	-	Oral presentation
P. Miller et al:	November 14-19 2004,	Multi-senor discrimination of harmful algal blooms (external travel funds).	XI International Conference On Harmful Algal Blooms	Cape Town, South Africa	Oral presentation Paper
B.G. Crespo, F.G. Figueiras	November 14-19 2004,	Coastal downwelling and dinoflagellate dominance in the Rías of Galicia.	XI International Conference On Harmful Algal Blooms	Cape Town, South Africa	Poster
F.G. Figueiras, B.G. Crespo, B. Arbones	November 14-19 2004,	Role of on-shore transport in HABs generation in the Rías Baixas of Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula).	XI International Conference On Harmful Algal Blooms	Cape Town, South Africa	Poster
P. Andersen:	November 14-19 2004,	the HABILE project – HAB's in large European Marine Ecosystems.	XI International Conference On Harmful Algal Blooms	Cape Town, South Africa	Poster

6.3 Near future scheduled publications

Authors	Title	Journal	Status
Johannessen, J.A, L.H. Pettersson, T. Eldevik, D. Durand, G. Evensen, N. Winther and Ø. Breivik	Chapter 5: Coastal Physical Processes.	In Remote Sensing Handbook, Editor Jim Gower.	Accepted to be published in 2005
L.H. Pettersson, D. Durand, D. Pozdnyakov, P. Andersen and O.M.	Monitoring of harmful algae blooms - the contribution by remote sensing	Book to be published by Praxis/Springer in	Under writing – draft manuscript of 3 of 5 major

Authors	Title	Journal	Status
Johannessen		2005	Chapters
Peter I. Miller, Jamie D. Shutler, Gerald F. Moore and Steve B. Groom	SeaWiFS discrimination of harmful algal bloom evolution	Int. J. of remote sensing	Progressed towards publication
Folkestad, A. and L.H. Pettersson and D. Durand	Inter-comparison of ocean colour data products during algal blooms in the North Sea	Int. J. of remote sensing – MERIS Special issue	Submitted in review
Krawczyk, H., Neumann, A., Gerasch, B., Walzel, T.	Regional products for the Baltic Sea using MERIS data	Int. J. of remote sensing – MERIS Special issue	Submitted in review
Allan, J.I., J.T. Holt, F.J. Gilbert, and R. Torres	Towards the simulation of harmful algae bloom events using functional ecosystem models in restricted exchange environments	Harmful Algae	Submitted – under review
Crespo, F.G. Figueiras	Coastal downwelling and dinoflagellate dominance in the Rias of Galicia.	Aquatic Microbial Ecology	Submitted, April 2005
F.G. Figueiras, B.G. Crespo, B. Arbones	Role of on-shore transport in HABs generation in the Rias Baixas of Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula).	Limnology and Oceanography	To be completed in 2005
Folkestad, A., L.H. Pettersson, J.A. Johannessen and D. Durand	Validation of a hydro-optical model for the North Sea.	Applied Optics (tbc)	To be submitted August 2005
Are Folkestad	Hydro-optical properties of the North Sea waters – applications for monitoring of HAB's.	Ph.D. Thesis	Due October, 2005
Kerstin Ebert	Detection, discrimination and monitoring of HABs by satellite remote sensing.	Ph.D. thesis	Due end 2006
F.G. Figueiras et al.	The influence of a spring poleward current on the distribution of phytoplankton assemblages along the western Iberian coast.	TDB	Historical data re-analysed in the framework of HABILE
F.G. Figueiras et al.	Annual cycle of plankton size-fractionated (pico-, nano- and microplankton) biomass in the Ria de Vigo.	TDB	Historical data re-analysed in the framework of HABILE
Naustvoll, Karlsson & Andersen 2003.	<i>Chattonella</i> blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak area. 1. Ecological profile of <i>Chattonella</i> spp.		Draft - submission in 2005
Naustvoll, Karlsson & Andersen, Durand, Pettersson 2003.	<i>Chattonella</i> blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak area. 2. Bloom dynamics in the period 1997-2002.		“
Karlsson, Naustvoll & Andersen, Pettersson et al. 2003..	<i>Chattonella</i> blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak area. 3. The role of physical forcing and nutrient load/availability on the formation of <i>Chattonella</i> blooms		“
Andersen, Karlsson & Naustvoll, Pettersson et al., 2003.	<i>Chattonella</i> blooms in the North Sea/Skagerrak area. 4. Conceptual models for bloom formation, origin and spreading in time and space.		“
Hense I., Stipa, T.	Phytoplankton and cyanobacteria bloom development in the Gulf of Finland.	TBD	Submission in 2005
Kaitala S., Fleming V., Hällfors S.	Occurrence of cyanobacteria in relation to nutrients and temperature	TBD	Submission in 2005

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